

INTERNATIONAL METADATA RECOMMENDATIONS AND PLATFORM-SPECIFIC REQUIREMENTS FOR OPEN ACCESS BOOKS AND CHAPTERS

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With a review of emerging policies and recommendations, an overview of metadata formats used in long-form publishing, specific metadata requirements mandated by international aggregators, and a formulation of a two-tiered metadata framework for books and chapters.

Contributor details:

- Tobias Steiner, Thoth Open Metadata, [0000-0002-3158-3136](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3158-3136)
- Javier Arias, Thoth Open Metadata & Open Book Publishers, [0000-0002-1963-4447](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1963-4447)
- Miranda Bennett, California Digital Library, [0000-0002-6225-1046](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6225-1046)
- Emma Booth, University of Manchester Library, [0009-0008-1390-2720](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-1390-2720)
- Jeff Edmunds, Pennsylvania State University Library, [0000-0002-0069-516X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0069-516X)
- Rupert Gatti, Thoth Open Metadata & Open Book Publishers, [0000-0003-0676-9024](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0676-9024)
- Ross Higman, Open Book Publishers
- Hannah Hillen, Thoth Open Metadata, [0009-0004-9521-0445](https://orcid.org/0009-0004-9521-0445)
- Mikael Laakso, Tampere University, [0000-0003-3951-7990](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3951-7990)
- Mike Nason, University of New Brunswick & Public Knowledge Project, [0000-0001-5527-8489](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5527-8489)
- Brendan O'Connell, Open Book Publishers
- Aleš Pogačnik, Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (ZRC SACU), [0000-0001-5100-9062](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5100-9062)
- Ursula Rabar, OPERAS, [0009-0008-7452-3732](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-7452-3732)
- Amanda Ramalho, Thoth Open Metadata & SciELO Livros, [0000-0002-9753-891X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9753-891X)
- Graham Stone, OAPEN Foundation, [0000-0002-5189-373X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5189-373X)
- Vincent W.J. van Gerven Oei, Thoth Open Metadata & punctum books, [0000-0003-1637-4261](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1637-4261)
- Zoe Wake Hyde, Public Knowledge Project, [0000-0002-9523-6635](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9523-6635)

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Acronyms

ARK	Archival Resource Key
APC	Article Processing Charge
BIBFRAME	Bibliographic Framework
BPC	Book Processing Charge
COAR	Confederation of Open Access Repositories
COMET	Collaborative Metadata Enhancement Task Force
COPIM	Community-led Open Publishing Infrastructures for Monographs
CSV	Comma-separated Values
DOAB	Directory for Open Access Books
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional open Access publishing Models to Advance Scholarly communication
CRAFT-OA	Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access
EQSIP	Equitable Standard for Institutional Publishing
JSTOR	Journal Storage
KBART	Knowledge Bases And Related Tools
JASPER	JournAIS are Preserved forevER
MARC	Machine-Readable Cataloging
NISO	National Information Standards Organization
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative – Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
ONIX	Online Information Exchange
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PALOMERA	Policy Alignment of Open access Monographs in the European Research Area
PID	Persistent Identifier
RNIB	Royal National Institute of the Blind
ROR	Research Organization Registry
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation

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I. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Drawing from multiple perspectives of not-for-profit Diamond OA book publishers, librarians, and open infrastructures, this report provides a comprehensive review of international metadata standards and requirements for open access books and chapters. It aims to support small-to-medium-sized independent scholar-led, as well as institutional, publishers of open access books in implementing effective metadata management practices, thereby improving the discoverability, interoperability, and sustainability of both closed and open access books.

The report situates Thoth Open Metadata within a broader movement towards open, community-owned infrastructure for scholarly publishing, responding to persistent challenges faced by independent and institutional publishers navigating proprietary metadata systems and fragmented technical standards. By consolidating research from major initiatives, including the ongoing work within the Copim Community as well as now-completed European initiatives such as [DIAMAS](#), [CRAFT-OA](#), and [PALOMERA](#), and the corresponding emergence of the journals-focused Diamond OA Standard ([DOAS](#)), this report outlines current policy landscapes, identifies key gaps, and proposes a harmonised approach to metadata for open access books.

Key findings include:

- Metadata openness and interoperability are critical for inclusion of books (open access and non-open access) in research assessment, policy development and monitoring, and equitable dissemination;
- Legal and accessibility frameworks (e.g., EU GPSR, Americans with Disabilities Act) necessitate the provision of richer metadata, including funder data, licensing, and accessibility fields, flowing through degradation-free metadata supply chains;
- Fragmentation of metadata standards and formats (ONIX, MARC, KBART, etc.) in use across stakeholders and intermediaries active in the supply chain impedes visibility and reuse of open access books, while also impinging on the reuse of the metadata itself;
- Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) such as DOI, ORCID, and ROR are essential for tracking, attribution, and interoperability – yet adoption remains uneven, particularly in the Humanities and Social Sciences, and within the wide archipelago of small-to-medium-sized publishers across the globe.
- The highly fragmented nature of the book supply chain – with an existing multiplicity of distribution channels and correspondingly fragmented metadata requirements that differs substantially from that of journal publishing – means that policy and technical maturity for open access books has traditionally lagged behind that of journals.

In response, the report proposes a two-tiered metadata framework:

- **Essential:** essential bibliographic and access data including information on title and subtitle, contributors, copyright holder, subjects, landing page and full-text URLs and/or DOIs at book and chapter level, licences, publisher details, and publication date.
Releasing metadata into the public domain and making this explicit in the metadata record (e.g., via a CC0 dedication) to facilitate easy re-use e.g., by libraries.
- **Desirable:** includes elements such as a fuller set of Persistent Identifiers (ORCID, ROR), and controlled vocabularies, multilingual metadata, abstracts, cover images, tables of contents, contributor affiliation, and funder details.

The proposed metadata framework aligns with emerging international quality standards and policy documents (e.g., Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS), the German Working Group of University Publishers' [AG Universitätsverlage] Quality Criteria, NISO recommendations, and existing policies such as the Swedish National Open Access policy or UKRI's Open Access policy¹). A more detailed description of the two-tiered metadata framework is available in [Section X](#).

This report also provides guidance for stakeholders to facilitate integration with key discovery platforms such as OAPEN, DOAB, Google Books, JSTOR, and Project MUSE, while also looking at traditional as well as alternative distribution mechanisms to academic libraries, considering that traditional library supply chains and distribution mechanisms are not up to the task of properly disseminating open access titles. Hence, alternative open mechanisms are needed to embed open access books more fully within library collections.

We call for coordination between stakeholders across open scholarly infrastructure to foster interoperability via a broader adoption of a common open metadata framework, with the overarching goals of empowering independent as well as institutional small-to-medium-sized publishers, enhancing discoverability, and strengthening bibliodiversity. By proposing a future-proof enhanced metadata framework, we intend to offer a pathway to more centrally position open access long-form publishing in the global scholarly communication ecosystem.

¹ A more detailed overview of extant policies is available via the PALOMERA project's findings report (Laakso et. al., 2024). A variety of policies are also documented in the PALOMERA [Knowledge Base](#).

II. INTRODUCTION

Metadata are integral to scholarly communication, affecting a broad range of stakeholders including publishers, service providers, researchers, funders, librarians, and data curators. During the last few years, a number of reports such as the 2019 [Science Europe briefing](#), or more recent initiatives such as the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) and the [COMET](#) community of practice have all stressed the importance of high-quality open technical metadata – covering bibliographic information, digital identifiers (e.g., DOI, ORCID, ROR), affiliation and funder/grant information, and open-access-specific elements – and called for harmonised standards across the sector. And although their critical role in discovery and accessibility is widely acknowledged, persistent challenges in standardisation and implementation of metadata for books and chapters impact both open access² and pay-to-read, closed access long-form publishing.

To address issues particular to book publishing, many experts have recommended the adoption of best practices and minimum metadata requirements for books to streamline workflows and enhance discoverability. Initiatives such as the formulation of the Jisc/OAPEN metadata model (2016), the outcomes of a 2018 Jisc workshop (Stone, 2018), and more recent research by, e.g., Grimme et al. (2021), Clarke & Ricci (2021), and Stone et al. (2021) support these recommendations. Likewise, academic libraries have been working to establish recommendations and sets of minimum metadata requirements to facilitate uptake of the digital long-form, see, e.g., the NISO Recommended Practice (2022), or the UK National Acquisition Group's work on establishing MARC21 Metadata Profiles for Print and Electronic Books (Booth, 2021).

And, as highlighted in the literature (Deville et al. 2016] Adema and Stone [2017 Stone et al. 2021 and Barnes et al. 2025), while enriched metadata can increase visibility and usage of OA books, creating and maintaining this data remains resource-intensive, and the landscape is difficult to navigate, particularly for smaller publishers. This is also reflected in publisher responses documented in a recent publication by Shaw and colleagues, stating:

Creation and distribution of metadata is an ongoing challenge. Although there are established industry standards such as ONIX and MARC, virtually all third-party distributors, discovery tools and other intermediaries require their own versions of these standards (if not their own proprietary data standard). Creating these metadata feeds and delivering them is a challenge for small and medium-sized publishers. (Shaw et al., 2023)

² For the purpose of this report, the authors are sympathetic to the PALOMERA project's definition of open access books as encompassing "scholarly, peer-reviewed books including monographs, book chapters, edited collections, critical editions, and other long-form scholarly work" (Bandura-Morgan et al. 2024), while also keeping an open mind to include other manifestations such as open textbooks and other, more experimental forms of long-form publishing (see e.g., Adema et al. 2022).

To tackle such issues, a group of independent scholar-led publishers, infrastructure providers, and researchers have come together to establish a fully open and freely available metadata platform, [Thoth](#), to empower any publisher to integrate the creation and management of high-quality open publication metadata within their internal publishing workflows.

This platform is currently operated by Thoth Open Metadata, a community- and values-led not-for-profit Community Interest Company registered in the UK. Thoth Open Metadata is designed to provide fully open solutions to the many barriers faced particularly by small independent scholar-led as well as institutional university- and/or library-led publishers when considering effective metadata creation, management, and subsequent dissemination to the wider book supply chain.

This report is one of the key deliverables to be released in the context of Thoth Open Metadata's role as a major stakeholder in the Copim Open Book Futures (OBF) project, funded jointly by the Research England Development Fund/UKRI and Arcadia between May 2023 and April 2026. Led by Lancaster University, OBF builds upon the pioneering work of the Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs (COPIM) project (2019–2023), with the aim to initiate a step-change in the ambition, scope, and impact of community-led open access book publishing.

From its inception, Thoth was conceived as an open dissemination platform (Stone et al. 2021), with the dedicated goal to enable open, transparent, and free access to efficient management and dissemination of open metadata and content within the scholarly book supply chain. And while Thoth has been developed with a particular focus on open access long-form scholarship, the platform is also capable of creating and managing open metadata for closed-access titles and chapters.

Alongside building the actual Thoth platform as a fully open-source and not-for-profit alternative to existing closed, commercial solutions, Thoth Open Metadata also makes its underlying research into open standards and infrastructures accessible to a wide range of users that would otherwise have difficulty with navigating the variety of specialist information available. Addressing the issues outlined, e.g., by Shaw et al. above, Thoth Open Metadata is also making its operational metadata management platform available for free, thus providing publishers with the means to efficiently create rich metadata for their titles and chapters, and enabling them to export that data into multiple metadata formats that are required for active participation in the wider book supply chain.

The report will first take a closer look at existing recommendations and requirements specific to book publishing on the level of policymaking and research, with a goal of situating the academic long form within the larger context of scholarly communications.

This is also done to specify some of the metadata and dissemination-specific differences between short-form journals publishing and the academic long form. In this context, the serial nature of journals has led to a consolidation of technical standards (with JATS XML

as the main quasi-standard). As the report shows, book publishing, with its complex multiplicity of output formats and corresponding plurality of technical standards and dissemination channels, presents quite a strong contrast to the rather uniform model of journals. These complexities have contributed to the hesitancy with which policy makers have engaged with long form open access publications to date.

Following that, the report will then provide an overview of the main metadata formats in use within the international book supply chain, before considering specific metadata requirements that aggregator platforms have established. Taking these different perspectives into account, the report then closes with the proposition of a dedicated, two-tiered set of essential and desirable metadata relevant to book publishers as well as the wider book supply chain, including aggregators, indices, libraries, and archiving solutions.

III. A REVIEW OF RECENT REPORTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS PERTAINING TO LONG-FORM PUBLISHING

“Expertise, knowledge, and experience in all areas of digital scholarly publishing are lacking among most Croatian book publishers. That becomes even more obvious from the information on hosting domains, or from the prevalence of permanent identifiers. The inability to comply with the established interoperability standards is seriously compromising the visibility and discoverability of book content, despite its open availability.” (Zlodi 2023)

During the past four years there has been increased activity particularly around Diamond OA publishing (see, e.g., Barnes et al. 2025), mostly focused on journals but in the book space as well, and with a strong representation of European projects and initiatives including COPIM, cOAlition S, DIAMAS, CRAFT-OA, and PALOMERA. This report starts with revisiting the dedicated webinar series “Voices from the Open Access Books Community” jointly organised by the Open Access Book Network and COPIM (Morka, 2021), before turning to a set of recommendations that had initially been published as part of the scoping research on open dissemination for books as part of the original COPIM project (Stone et al. 2021). This will be followed by a review of the Extensible Quality Standard in Institutional Publishing (EQSIP), DIAMAS Quality evaluation criteria, best practices, and assessment systems for Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) (Armengou et al. 2025; Armengou et al. 2023; Ševkušić and Kuchma 2023), and Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS), before then also looking at the Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area (PALOMERA) report (Laakso et al. 2024).

Additionally, it warrants highlighting here that while EQSIP had initially considered criteria for both short- and long-form publishing, the scope of the resulting Diamond Open Access Standard (Consortium of the DIAMAS Project, 2025) was refined to only apply to journals. For the specific purpose of collecting recommendations related to long-form publishing, it thus seemed of interest to take into account the results of the EQSIP consultations where they are pertinent to books, and then also look at the journal-focused Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) to see which of the proposed elements might warrant adoption to long-form publishing.

“Voices from the Open Access Books Community” Webinars (2021)

During 2020 and 2021, the Open Access Books Network (OABN) conducted a series of webinars focusing on different topics pertaining to OA book publishing. Their “Voices from the Open Access Books Community” summary (Morka 2021) provides a good snapshot of issues faced by those active in long-form publishing.

The discussions highlight the complexity of metadata for OA books, noting that challenges extend beyond technical implementation, encompassing political and policy considerations. Variations in understanding across scholarly communities coupled with a lack of consistent guidance hinder the development of effective metadata standards. Participants note that unlike OA journals, OA book publishing seems less advanced in fulfilling technical requirements, and policy frameworks such as Plan S cannot be directly transposed without adaptation.

Participants acknowledge that definitions of “high-quality” metadata remain contested, with proposals ranging from discipline-specific minimum records to more general guidelines. Such a lack of consensus undermines the capacity to track and assess the outputs and impacts of OA books, particularly in relation to policy evaluation. It is understood that metadata serves multiple purposes, and it can thus be difficult (if not impossible) to arrive at a universal definition that combines the variety of priorities that different stakeholders bring to the metaphorical table. It was noted as well that issues also arise in managing metadata for backlist catalogues.

Workshop attendees further noted that multiplicity and inconsistency across metadata schemas further complicate discoverability and create duplication risks (e.g., when multiple DOIs are minted for the same work³). It was raised that clear distinctions between different metadata types (e.g., content, abstracts, media, formats) would be necessary, alongside provisions for accessibility. It was highlighted that chapter-level metadata is increasingly relevant, though technically challenging. Compliance with the requirements of diverse services (e.g., Zenodo, OpenAIRE, Crossref) varies globally, and the openness of metadata collections remains uneven. Initiatives such as the Thoth platform offer potential for an open, community-owned approach, but national and institutional variations persist. Interoperability between metadata standards and formats, particularly across supply chain and library systems, is deemed an essential feature – but existing mappings between standards and formats remain lossy, thus resulting in degraded metadata at the end of a data conversion chain. Hence, a central open source of truth for quality metadata with a flexible metadata model that can support exports to different formats without compromising the original dataset would be ideal. Smaller publishers face resource constraints, and policy recommendations must accommodate bibliodiversity and avoid excluding them.

Persistent identifiers (PIDs), including ORCID and DOI, are recognised as crucial for visibility and interoperability, though multiple barriers such as associated costs, software limitations, questions of entity management, mapping between different PIDs, and disciplinary differences with regards to adoption – especially in the Humanities and the Social Sciences – have been noted. PID metadata is critical for discoverability, but incomplete updating by authors, inconsistencies in national practices, and reliance on manual processes contribute to identification errors. Training for both authors and publishers was noted as essential to improve PID use and metadata quality.

³ For more detailed documentation on this issue, see van Gerven Oei et al. (2025).

In summary, the literature and recent empirical research collectively underscore that OA book policies ought to be developed with sensitivity to the specificities of long-form scholarly publishing. Critical areas for intervention include improving metadata quality and openness, ensuring the use of PIDs, addressing the uneven implementation of legal deposit frameworks, and enhancing technical infrastructure. These efforts should be grounded in inclusive, flexible policy frameworks that reflect the varied realities of stakeholders across the scholarly communication ecosystem.

COPIM's Building an Open Dissemination System Report (2021)

Building on the foundational research conducted in the context of the formulation of the Jisc/OAPEN metadata model (2016), the outcomes of a 2018 Jisc workshop (Stone 2018), and more recent research (Grimme et al. 2021 Clarke & Ricci 2021), the recommendations distilled from Stone et al. (2021) propose a two-tier metadata framework.

The authors suggest for this two-tiered metadata framework to comprise minimum and enriched requirements, with chapter-level metadata included within the minimum set (Rec. 14). DOIs at both title and chapter level have also been identified as in-scope for minimum requirements (Rec. 53). The scoping report also noted technical specifications should incorporate updated MARC 21 fields 506, 540, and 856 (Rec. 45) and consider the CODEX standard (Rec. 48).⁴ Enriched metadata should enable the inclusion of subject codes, author-generated keywords, and tables of contents (Rec. 52)⁵.

Further recommendations address the automation of ORCID implementation for all contributors (Rec. 55), monitoring of evolving identifier systems such as the Funder Registry (Rec. 56), ROR, and ISNI (Rec. 57), and RAiD (Rec. 58). Additional considerations include the incorporation of a “free of charge” pricing element (Rec. 60) and support for non-standard Latin script forms in metadata (Rec. 61).

With a view on metadata outputs, the recommendations address the dissemination and discovery of metadata. Beyond ensuring high-quality metadata, the team was tasked with determining optimal delivery mechanisms and maintenance of a set of up-to-date output templates to support diverse dissemination channels. Such templates, it was noted, would enable publishers to select relevant discovery routes – both traditional and emerging – and identify the corresponding minimum metadata requirements. Longer-term maintenance of, and periodic updates to, these templates was highlighted as a key challenge.

The recommendations emphasise the need to engage with major discovery platforms and standards, including understanding Amazon’s backend systems (Rec. 23) and

⁴ The most recent version of FOLIO’s CODEX documentation (April 10, 2023) notes that “as of the Nolana release (Q3 2022) the Codex app was retired”.

⁵ It is worth noting here that particularly the provision of information on Subjects has gained more traction, with recent research published via [NISO](#) and [NAG-SUPC](#) considering this type of information as essential metadata.

algorithms alongside broader SEO practices catering to Google’s ecosystem (incl. Google Books) (Rec. 25). Testing interoperability with tools such as Zotero (Rec. 29) and exploring integration with networks such as H-Net (Rec. 32) are also advised. The open dissemination system was envisioned to be able to generate MARC records for OA monographs under open licences to facilitate reuse (Rec. 33).

Technical outputs should include high-quality ONIX feeds at both title and chapter levels (Rec. 43), BIBFRAME exports for library discovery systems (Rec. 46)⁶, and KBART files tested with partner institutions to ensure availability as subscription packages in library systems (Rec. 50).

NISO RP-29-2022, E-Book Bibliographic Metadata Requirements in the Sale, Publication, Discovery, Delivery, and Preservation Supply Chain (2022) & NAG Quality of Shelf-Ready Metadata Survey and recommendations (2021)

In 2022, the National Information Standards Organization (NISO) published a dedicated set of recommendations targeted at e-books. High-quality e-book metadata is understood as an essential infrastructure for the modern book supply chain, supporting discovery, acquisition, delivery, and preservation across publishers, vendors, libraries, and retailers. The corresponding NISO document RP-29-2022 addresses persistent inconsistencies in how metadata is created and exchanged, and sets out recommendations to improve interoperability and trust.

At the core of the report is the argument that metadata must reliably support three functions: identification of a book, record-matching across systems, and differentiating between editions, versions, and formats. NISO stresses that publishers should remain the authoritative source for core metadata, and that downstream providers are advised to avoid overwriting publisher-supplied information with conflicting values. Equally important is metadata provenance – metadata should be accurate, traceable, and governed as a lifecycle asset, not treated as static descriptive text.

The report’s most consequential element-level recommendations focus on five metadata categories:

1. **Titles** should be clean and consistent, excluding promotional text and maintaining structured title/subtitle formatting to support automated matching.
2. **Names** should follow standard formatting and, where possible, be connected to authority identifiers (e.g., ISNI or VIAF) to reduce ambiguity.
3. **Dates** should be unambiguous and differentiated (publication, release, copyright, update), using standardized formats such as ISO-8601.

⁶ It seems pertinent to highlight the nature of the recommendations included in the initial open dissemination system report (as well as other reports and recommendations referenced in this section) are documents representative of their times – and the ODS report was published at the early stages of a slowly-emerging focus on OA book metadata. Stakeholder groups’ priorities may have evolved, and different sets of development focus points may have emerged since.

4. **Identifiers** are deemed central: ISBNs should be consistently assigned and unique per edition and format, supplemented by additional identifiers (e.g., DOI, LCCN) when available.
5. **Subjects** should rely on controlled vocabularies (e.g., BISAC, Thema, LCSH), clearly separated from free-text keywords, to improve cross-platform discoverability.

Beyond these core elements, NISO also highlights the operational importance of metadata for format, rights constraints, and persistent links (URIs), particularly as the industry moves toward linked-data environments.

Overall, NISO's key message is that book metadata quality is not a local concern: inconsistencies propagate across the supply chain. The implementation of standardised identifiers, authority control, controlled vocabularies, and provenance-aware workflows substantially improves discovery, reduces duplication, and enables scalable delivery and preservation.

The findings of the NISO report also broadly overlap with recommendations of the UK National Acquisitions Group (NAG). Following the collection of feedback from more than 50 UK institutions, the 2021 NAG Quality of Shelf-Ready Metadata Survey and recommendations (Booth 2021) likewise identify the above five metadata elements as essential, while also highlighting additional attributes such as information on a book's format, constraints on use, and usage of Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs). Doing so, the NAG research provides valuable evidence from the perspective of academic libraries on essential and desirable book metadata elements for the purposes of enabling discovery and access of long-form publications.

Extensible Quality Standard in Institutional Publishing (EQSIP) (2023, 2024), IPSP Best Practices Quality Evaluation Criteria, Best Practices, and Assessment Systems for Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) (2023), and the Diamond Open Access Standard (2025)

Under the remit of the DIAMAS project, a formulation of an aspirational gold standard for open access outputs was published, which represents "a measure of quality that IPSPs strive to meet, and that serves as a point of reference against which current IPSPs may be compared, and that they can hopefully conform to in good time and with appropriate support" (Armengou et al. 2023).

The initial scoping exercise conducted in the context of this development work considered aspects relevant for both short- and long-form publishing and led to the publication of a first version of the Extensible Quality Standard in Institutional Publishing (EQSIP). Following subsequent refinement, a second version of EQSIP (Rico-Castro et al. 2024) had a reduced scope on short-form journals publishing – and this in turn informed the formulation of the Diamond Open Access Standard (Consortium of the DIAMAS Project 2025).

The results of this scoping exercise are deemed of interest to this report, as they provide insights into a broader discussion around open access publishing, and diamond open access in particular, with respondents drawn from a wide range of institutional and other publishing initiatives. And while the results distilled in DOAS are mostly relevant to journal publishing, there are some elements of the initial EQSIP consultation that remain pertinent to books.

Taking a broader-stroke approach to metadata, the requirements outlined in the Extensible Quality Standard in Institutional Publishing (EQSIP) (Armengou et al. 2023) mandate that each scholarly item should possess a unique, persistent identifier (preferably a DOI) and a dedicated landing page containing comprehensive metadata in both human- and machine-readable formats (e.g., HTML, XML via OAI-PMH, JSON). Required metadata include titles, author names and affiliations (with country/region), abstracts, keywords, funding details (funder name and grant identifier), standard numbers (e.g., ISSN, ISBN), and other relevant persistent identifiers (e.g., ORCID, ROR, Funder DOIs). CRediT taxonomy tags and conflict-of-interest statements must be encoded in JATS XML. Open access status, copyright, and licensing information are provided in standardised, non-proprietary formats. Complete metadata, including bibliographic references, are regularly deposited with registration agencies (e.g., Crossref) in alignment with I4OC and I4OA initiatives, and there are established protocols for transferring metadata to open repositories and aggregators.

Full-text content should be tagged in JATS XML or equivalent (e.g., TEI), offered in multiple digital formats (PDF, HTML, XML, ePub), and deposited in recognised preservation services. Publications should include high-resolution, accessible figures and tables, and link to underlying datasets, code, and supplementary outputs in external repositories.

It seems noteworthy that [JATS XML](#) is not commonly used in long-form publishing, as it comprises an XML schema particularly relevant to journals. There also is the Book Interchange Tag Set ([BITS](#)), an extension that has sought to introduce an additional set of book-related elements to JATS, but BITS has so far failed to see broader adoption across the book publishing landscape.

The recommendations published by Ševkušić and Kuchma mainly overlap with EQSIP, with a notable addition to ensure that “the metadata provided via commonly used metadata exchange protocols are available under the CC0 Public Domain Dedication” (Ševkušić and Kuchma 2023, 19).

Combining the earlier versions of EQSIP and the recommendations published by Ševkušić and Kuchma, the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) advocates for the provision of a core set of bibliographic metadata to ensure that both readers and indexing systems can interpret and trust the publication record. At minimum, such a core set for journals is recommended to comprise article titles, author names and affiliations, abstracts, keywords, journal title, ISSN/eISSN, publisher name, publication date, and citation information such as volume/issue and pagination (or article number where used).

The guidance also highlights the need to record funding information (at least funder name and grant identifier) and encourages use of persistent identifiers for funders and institutions. Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are likewise understood as essential. DOAS highlight the need to ensure that identifiers exist not only for the article (typically DOIs) but also for authors and contributors (via ORCID) and for affiliations and organizations (e.g., via ROR). Importantly, identifiers should not just be “present”: they should be displayed as active links wherever they appear, including in the full text, so that they can fulfil their function as navigational and verification tools. Further to that, the Diamond Open Access Standard guidelines recommend adding contributor role information, for example using the CRediT taxonomy, both on the landing page and within the full text of a given journal article. They also highlight the importance of including key transparency information such as open access status, copyright holder, and licensing. To support dissemination and ecosystem-wide reuse (including by indexing services and libraries), the guidance also recommends release of said publication metadata into the public domain, for example by applying a CC0 dedication. Regarding operationalisation of metadata dissemination, publishers are encouraged to clearly display the metadata licensing terms on a journal’s website and to provide the relevant technical endpoints (e.g., the OAI-PMH URL) or instructions for metadata harvesting.

Keeping the caveat of JATS (see above) in mind to highlight the often-significant differences between journal and book publishing and the resulting limits of applicability of journals-focused recommendations to a book publishing context, and also taking into account the two standards’ more general focus on journal publishing, both EQSIP and the Diamond OA Standard (2025) provide valuable pointers to metadata elements that will be useful to consider for adaptation to long-form publishing.

It is understood that some of the Diamond Open Access Standard recommendations will require further adjustments to be more fully applicable to the complexities of book publishing. For a fuller discussion of the differences between short-form journal publishing, and how this compares to long-form publishing of academic books such as monographs, edited collections, etc., see, e.g., Barnes et al. (2025).

Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area (PALOMERA) report (2024)

Taking the perceived lack of explicit engagement with long-form publishing on the level of policymaking as a starting point, the Horizon Europe-funded Policy Alignment of Open Access Monographs in the European Research Area (PALOMERA) project (2023–24) has recently published a substantive report to investigate the landscape of Open Access (OA) funder policies.

Tasked with conducting a comprehensive review of current OA book policy and practice across the European Research Area (ERA), and with national and institutional policies in

scope⁷, the authors highlight a strong fragmentation of the landscape of OA book policy and infrastructure on both conceptual as well as operational levels. Despite the central role of policy in shaping scholarly communications, a scarcity of comprehensive literature focusing specifically on OA books, as opposed to the relatively well-explored terrain of OA journal articles, is noted (Laakso et al. 2024, 43).

According to the authors, this gap in scholarship appears indicative of a broader lack of policy maturity surrounding OA monographs and long-form scholarly content. The authors highlight long-standing calls from experts for OA books policy to enable nuanced and targeted approaches, to account for the diversity of publishing practices and institutional contexts across the globe. In light of the increasing importance of Diamond Open Access to policy, the importance of operational models that move beyond Book Processing Charges (BPCs) (e.g., via consortial funding), and the crucial importance of technical infrastructure in facilitating dissemination and discoverability are highlighted (Laakso et al. 2024, 43ff).

Regarding technical recommendations, one of the report's key findings is the unexpectedly high value stakeholders place on openly available metadata, even ranking it above the simultaneous release of free digital book versions (Laakso et al., 2024, 46). This prioritisation highlights an understanding of metadata's central role in the discoverability, monitoring, and sustainability of OA books across an increasing number of stakeholders. The report strongly recommends that funders and policymakers place greater emphasis on openness of metadata in future OA frameworks.

In this regard, the adoption of persistent identifiers (PIDs) such as DOI and ORCID is identified as a critical technical standard. Their widespread use is seen as instrumental in improving long-term discoverability and enhancing the capacity for policy impact assessment (Laakso et al. 2024, 46, 53). Additionally, the report stresses the need for dedicated budget lines to enable libraries and other stakeholders to support OA publishing infrastructure, alongside encouragement for alternative formats, to enable publishers to move beyond the provision of conventional PDFs (Laakso et al., 2024, 46).

However, and in line with earlier research (e.g., Grimme et al., 2021; Clarke & Ricci 2021; and Stone et al. 2021), the authors acknowledge the persistence of significant technical and systemic barriers. One major obstacle identified is the lack of high-quality metadata across the OA book supply chain, which undermines efforts to track publication trends, assess policy compliance, and ensure equitable visibility – particularly for outputs from smaller publishers and non-English language contexts (Laakso et al. 2024, 113). The OpenAlex database, for instance, is shown to lack comprehensive metadata coverage for books and chapters, highlighting the necessity for improved DOI assignment and better representation of institutional affiliations in book records (Laakso et al. 2024, 53).

Legal deposit systems also emerge as a limiting factor; national variations in how legal deposit is structured and implemented lead to inconsistent and incomplete data

⁷ According to the study's authors, 650 policy and policy-related documents of 39 ERA countries were analysed, accompanied by over 40 anonymised interviews with stakeholders from across the ERA.

coverage. This resonates strongly with the findings of the National Libraries Network coordinated by the Archiving and Digital Preservation Group of Copim Open Book Futures (cf. Barnes 2024).

Further compounding these issues are infrastructural gaps in library integration and metadata dissemination (see also McCollough 2017; Morka and Gatti 2021).

With regards to recommendations for future policy development, Laakso and colleagues caution against prematurely enforcing highly standardised OA book policies across multiple institutions, countries, and regions. In contrast to the more mature journal ecosystem, the book publishing landscape is characterised by considerable variation in technological infrastructure, cultural practices, and institutional readiness. As such, the report advocates for context-sensitive policy development that accommodates national and institutional diversity while progressively working towards interoperable standards (Laakso et al. 2024, 133–34).

IV. KEY METADATA FORMATS RELEVANT IN BOOK PUBLISHING, AND THEIR FORMAL REQUIREMENTS

As discussed in more detail in van Gerven Oei (2021), and via the recommendations distilled from the scoping report informing the development of Thoth as an open dissemination system (Stone et al. 2021), the book publishing ecosystem is grappling with a plethora of different metadata formats and sub-specifications.

The graphic below provides a schematic overview of the variety of formats, platform-specific versions, and platforms using these specific, bespoke [variations of a given format](#).

Figure 1: Overview of metadata formats, particular specifications, and platforms for open access books. Graphic [CC BY 4.0](#) Thoth Open Metadata.

In the following, we will first be focusing on the three major metadata formats particular to the book supply chain, namely MARC, ONIX, and KBART. We will briefly touch on each format’s specifics, while also providing links to more detailed technical discussions. For each of those formats, we will also provide an indication of progress made so far with integrating this in the Thoth platform, while also outlining potential future work that remains to be done to make the provision of that format as easy as possible.

MARC - the key format for library cataloguing

MARC, short for MACHine-Readable Cataloging, refers to a standardised data format developed under the leadership of the US Library of Congress more than six decades ago. It enables computers to exchange, process, and interpret bibliographic data and forms the structural basis for most modern library catalogues (Library of Congress 2020). Initially developed as MARC, the format evolved into various regionally specific flavours (e.g., USMARC, UKMARC, and CANMARC). Some of these versions have then been consolidated to form MARC21 in the late 1990s. Today, MARC21 is the most extensively used version of MARC, making it the de facto standard as both a production and exchange format for libraries across the globe.

The ongoing maintenance of MARC21 is jointly managed by the Network Development and MARC Standards Office at the Library of Congress and the Standards and Support Office at Library and Archives Canada. Contributions to its development are drawn from a global community of stakeholders, including libraries, library networks, utilities, and library system vendors. MARC21 is commonly used in libraries across the globe, and many library systems now also support MARCXML, which is interoperable with other XML-based standards.⁸

Substantial work has been invested by Thoth to develop automated workflows designed to align with established practices and documentation related to the MARC standard, including guidance from the [Library of Congress](#).⁹ Thoth is now able to output **MARC21** as well as **MARCXML** specifications via its dedicated [Export API](#), for either a single book entry, or a publisher's whole catalogue.

Further details on MARC specifications:

- <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/MARC-21>
- <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/MARCXML>

⁸ In the following, the authors will be adding pointers to the [Thoth Wiki](#), which has been established by the Thoth team over the years to document and continuously log updates on progress made.

⁹ Thoth's MARC implementation has benefited significantly from expert contributions by Emma Booth (University of Manchester, UK), colleagues at Jisc (UK), and Jeffrey Edmunds (Pennsylvania State University Libraries, USA), whose insights have been invaluable. These consultations underscored the complexities inherent in the MARC standard, which – while highly structured and prescriptive in some respects – allows for considerable context-dependent interpretation in others. As such, despite efforts to automate the generation of MARC records, it remains quite impossible to achieve full automation without compromising data quality, with the final output of a given MARC record always depending on the accuracy and completeness of metadata supplied by a given publisher.

ONIX for Books – the standard format used by vendors & aggregators

ONIX for Books, maintained by the non-profit organisation EDItEUR, constitutes one of the most widely adopted metadata standards in the publishing industry. Originally developed through a collaboration between EDItEUR, Book Industry Communication (BIC, UK), and the Book Industry Study Group (BISG, US), it is now governed by an International Steering Committee. This committee includes not only the founding organisations but also representatives from [national user groups](#) in numerous countries, including Australia, Canada, China, France, Germany, Japan, and South Africa, and with a generally-notable focus on Global North representation of large businesses.

ONIX for Books serves as the international standard for the electronic representation and dissemination of bibliographic and product information within the global book industry.

Rather than prescribing a rigid format, ONIX is structured as an open XML schema. This flexibility has led to divergent implementations across platforms, each interpreting the schema to define its own version of a minimally viable ONIX record.

To support the application of ONIX for open access (OA) publications, EDItEUR provides a range of guidance materials, including a [Best Practice Guide for OA Books](#). A recently revised [Application Note](#) specifically addresses the description of open access monographs using ONIX versions 3.0 and 3.1. This document outlines metadata requirements specific to OA works, including the attribution of funding bodies (where applicable), the inclusion of a direct link to the open access licence, the provision of a simplified open access statement, and the use of an open access flag.

Additional metadata considerations relevant to OA monographs include the designation of free-of-charge access and the identification of repository locations from which the digital object can be retrieved. While these fields are not exclusive to OA publications, EDItEUR notes that they are infrequently used in commercial publishing contexts. With respect to funder acknowledgements, ONIX distinguishes these entities from contributors, categorising funders instead in a role analogous to that of a publisher – that is, as facilitators of research or publication, rather than as creators of content ([EDItEUR 2024](#)).

Over the past three years, Thoth has expanded and refined its support for multiple ONIX output formats. For ONIX 2.1, Thoth has implemented platform-specific requirements of EBSCOhost and ProQuest Ebrary, achieving full compatibility as validated through direct collaboration with both services.

With ONIX 3, Thoth is able to generate ONIX 3.0 exports that meet specifications from Project MUSE, OAPEN, JSTOR, Google Books, and OverDrive. In several instances, acquiring precise requirements from individual platforms has proven a time-intensive process, given the need to identify both the necessary data elements and their preferred representations in close exchange with the platforms. These platform-specific variations of the general metadata format will be addressed later in this report, see

section "[Metadata Requirements of International Repositories, Aggregators, and Indices](#)".

In addition to platform-specific exports, Thoth now has comprehensive ONIX 3.0 and ONIX 3.1.2 export variants available that include the full range of metadata fields as provided by publishers. These extended export formats, along with Thoth's JSON export, represent the most complete metadata output currently available from the platform, contrasting it with more constrained, platform-targeted exports. The added benefit of ONIX 3 over ONIX 2.1 is that it accommodates a wider set of PIDs (most notably ROR as a funder identifier), as well as the provision of open access licensing on a per-chapter basis. Thoth has further consulted with EDItEUR for an assessment of the current ONIX files generated by the Thoth export API.¹⁰

Furthermore, the Thoth team is addressing evolving legal and regulatory requirements by implementing an extension to its overall data schema. This will enable the inclusion of metadata fields necessary to comply with recent European Union legislation, such as the General Product Safety Regulation (GPSR), the European Accessibility Act, and the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA). See Sections VI through IX for further details on these specific requirements. These additions support publisher reporting related to accessibility, sustainability, and archival commitments, aligning metadata outputs with contemporary legal obligations. EDItEUR provides comprehensive and up-to-date guidance (via their [application notes](#)) on many of these issues, and the team will be working to implement these in Thoth's ONIX outputs in the coming months.

Further details on ONIX in Thoth:

- <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/ONIX-3>
- <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/ONIX-2.1>

KBART – transferring collection data to knowledge bases

KBART (Knowledge Bases and Related Tools) is a NISO Recommended Practice designed to standardise the transfer of holdings metadata from content providers to knowledge base suppliers and libraries. These knowledge bases are integral to the functionality of library link resolvers and electronic resource management systems.

Initially released in 2010 with a focus on journal metadata, KBART was expanded in Phase II (2014) to address more complex metadata challenges, including those related to consortia, open access content, e-books, and conference proceedings. In 2019, the "KBART Automation" Recommended Practice was introduced to enable the automated and accurate exchange of institution-specific holdings data between content providers

¹⁰ Thoth Open Metadata is immensely grateful to Graham Bell, Executive Director of EDItEUR, who provided a thorough review of two extensive sample catalogues by Open Book Publishers and punctum books. The review's outcomes are very encouraging, and the team at Thoth Open Metadata is now working to implement the recommendations together with a wider-ranging general update of Thoth's metadata schema to be released in Q1/2026.

and knowledge bases. This automation reduces the need for manual updates by library staff and ensures systems accurately reflect institutional access.

Phase III, launched in December 2019, aims to further enhance the standard by improving support for diverse content types and global resources, refining endorsement protocols, and providing clearer implementation guidance and examples. The Phase III public draft of KBART, which has been made available for public consultation between Sept 19 and Nov 15, 2025, highlights some particularities of the KBART format. For one, and due to its focus on the level of collections, the KBART approach only provides information on the book/title-level entity, with no way to include chapter-level information. Regarding classification of work types, KBART maintains the dichotomy of "monograph" vs. "serial" to highlight ongoing versus one-time release patterns, and no other work type classifications permitted. And particularly relevant to Open Access books, a description of OA titles remains complicated, as this requires a combination of three different elements that combined mark a book "freely available".¹¹

Continuing its conversations with the [NISO KBART standards committee](#), Thoth has improved its KBART output to align with OCLC's specifications. The output can also be used to submit data to ProQuest / Ex Libris and EBSCO's Knowledge Bases, among many others.

Thoth Open Metadata is listed in the official [KBART registry](#), a directory of organisations committed to improving e-resource linking by providing their metadata information to the supply chain. According to communications with the NISO KBART standards committee, official KBART endorsement appears to not be available for facilitator platforms such as Thoth – rather, endorsements are given on a per-publisher level. Publishers seeking [KBART endorsement](#) for their metadata records will find that the Thoth format now makes this easy to obtain.

Further details on KBART specifications:

- <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/KBART>

¹¹ According to the [KBART draft document](#) (accessed Oct 10, 2025), the challenge of identifying free-to-read (open-access) content in a KBART file is significant because these files are designed to delineate content accessible through a purchased collection. With the exception of the "All Titles" file, a KBART file's data represents the access rights for a specific acquired collection. Importantly, KBART files communicate title-level information, and therefore do not support the communication of article-, chapter-, or issue-level free access (such as hybrid open access). Consequently, identifying free content must be accomplished using a combination of three elements: statement of file type, the coverage statement (including start/end dates, volume, issue, and embargo), and access type.

BIBFRAME

BIBFRAME has been introduced in its current specification in 2016 as a potential replacement for MARC, yet, as Stone et al. (2021) and others have noted, MARC remains widely used as the de facto standard in library systems. With the rise of web-scale discovery tools, some experiments with BIBFRAME have emerged in some corners (particularly with national libraries such as the Library of Congress, the British Library, and a number of European libraries) due to its promises of implementing a Linked Data paradigm (Tharani, 2015), leveraging the RDF modelling practice of uniquely identifying as Web resources all entities, attributes, and relationships (i.e., properties) between entities.

Thoth Open Metadata will continue to keep a watching brief on further developments around BIBFRAME, and potentially consider implementation of a dedicated export.

Further details on BIBFRAME:

- <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/BIBFRAME-2.0>

CODEX

In the context of the [FOLIO open-source LMS community](#), a metadata model called CODEX, inspired by both BIBFRAME and Dublin Core, had been introduced. Stone et al. (2021) list CODEX as one of the models worth investigating further, but as of 2023, the most recent version of FOLIO's CODEX documentation (April 10, 2023) notes that "as of the Nolana release (Q3 2022) the Codex app was retired". At the time of writing, it is unclear if the underlying CODEX data model is still being used.

Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH)

The Open Archives Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting ([OAI-PMH](#)) is a standardised framework enabling repositories and services to exchange metadata efficiently. Operating over HTTP, it uses URL-based requests with case-sensitive parameters encoded in the query section, and returns responses in XML format. The protocol defines six core operations - Identify, GetRecord, ListMetadataFormats, ListIdentifiers, ListRecords, and ListSets - which facilitate the structured harvesting and sharing of metadata across systems.

Different flavours of OAI-PMH called application schemata have evolved over time, with the most generic one implementing Dublin Core in `oai_dc`. Another widely used schema is that of OpenAIRE, via `oai_oaire`. Thoth Open Metadata is currently working to expose its database via a dedicated OAI-PMH endpoint, implementing both of these schemata. The OAI-PMH endpoint is scheduled to go live in Q1/2026.

Many open knowledge graphs such as [OpenAIRE](#) or [OpenAlex](#) rely on OAI-PMH to harvest content for inclusion in their databases, and following the provision of a

dedicated OAI-PMH endpoint, Thoth Open Metadata will seek to work with these initiatives to ensure the Open Access book and chapter metadata provided by the many publishers using Thoth are being harvested by and indexed in those graphs.

More information on OAI-PMH:

- <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/OAI-PMH>

OPDS

OPDS (Open Publication Distribution System) is an open standard based on Atom and, more recently, JSON, designed for the distribution and discovery of digital publication catalogues. First introduced in 2010 by a consortium of developers of digital reading applications and publishing organisations, OPDS provides a standardised way to browse, discover, and access e-books across devices and platforms.

Originally developed as an extension of the Atom Syndication Format, OPDS enabled not only the listing of bibliographic information for digital publications but also seamless integration with reading systems and digital libraries. Over time, the specification has evolved into [OPDS 2.0](#), a modernised JSON-based version maintained by the Radium Foundation, which has gained adoption within the digital reading and library community.

OPDS is particularly relevant to the open access publishing ecosystem, as it facilitates decentralised, open distribution of catalogues, and allows publishers, libraries, and distributors to expose their entire collections in a lightweight, machine-readable format. While OPDS does not aim to provide the same level of bibliographic and commercial detail as ONIX, it plays a key role in dissemination and discovery by making open catalogues easily accessible to readers and integrable into reading applications such as [Thorium Reader](#).

Thoth Open Metadata is keeping a watching brief on further developments with OPDS, with plans to potentially implement OPDS in 2026.

More information on OPDS:

- <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/OPDS>

Comma-separated values (CSV)

While not formally a dedicated metadata format, the practice of generating plain-text output via comma-separated values (CSV) remains a widely used fallback option to facilitate transmission of data across systems. CSV is defined by the [RFC4180](#) standard.

Within Thoth, an automated ingest option is being implemented that enables publishers to upload CSV or ONIX files of their existing book catalogue into the Thoth database.

The ingest engine will then parse uploaded data and provide a preview of how book details are being mapped onto the Thoth data model. A publisher can then choose to either continue with the ingest, or return to the file in question to review missing data fields if they wish to do so.

A CSV export is also available on both the individual book level as well as for the full catalogue of a publisher via Thoth's metadata outputs.

More information on CSV:

- <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/CSV>

Archival Resource Key (ARK)

Archival Resource Keys (ARKs) are persistent identifiers designed to provide stable, non-breaking URLs for information objects, supported by the international [ARK Alliance](#).

Unlike other PIDs such as DOIs, Handles, and PURLs, which depend on centralised resolution systems, ARKs are decentralised identifiers that can be registered and used by participating organisations within ca. 48 hours.

More information on ARK:

- <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/ARK>

JSON

JSON ([JavaScript Object Notation](#)) is a lightweight, text-based format for exchanging structured data. Standardized as ECMA-404 and RFC 8259, it is language-independent despite its roots in JavaScript and is designed to be both human-readable and easy for machines to process. JSON represents data using a small set of types – objects, arrays, strings, numbers, booleans, and null – combined with simple, strict syntax rules. Its simplicity and wide interoperability have made it a default choice for web APIs, configuration files, and data serialization, even though it intentionally omits features such as comments, schemas, and specialized data types.

JSON exports are available through the Thoth export API. The JSON export represents the fullest representation of a book record's data available through Thoth, and it is this format that is being included as a 'sidecar' file in archival deposits with generalist repositories (see below), to provide future generations with as much contextual metadata as possible.

More information on JSON:

- <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/JSON>

V. METADATA REQUIREMENTS OF INTERNATIONAL REPOSITORIES, AGGREGATORS, AND INDICES

The management and distribution of book metadata is further complicated by the overlay of extensive platform-specific requirements of each individual repository, aggregator, and index that distributes book metadata, as well as an abundant variety of data ingest processes. An overview of these requirements is given below, while a detailed comparison of relevant metadata fields required by each platform is provided in the report's supplementary spreadsheet:

[Overview of International Aggregators' Metadata Requirements for Books](#)

Thoth Open Metadata has established a variety of metadata outputs that adhere to each platform's specifications. Publishers can generate each of these for free via the self-service Thoth open metadata management platform, with exports available on a per-book and full-catalogue level.

For publishers seeking to automate and streamline their dissemination workflows, Thoth Open Metadata has subscription-based dissemination services available, which take care of data submission to the variety of platforms described in the following segments. These services also enable small publishers to benefit from free Crossref membership through Thoth Open Metadata's Crossref sponsorship, with automated registration of DOIs then facilitated via automated workflows, as well as discounts on various dissemination platforms.

OAPEN Library and the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB)

The OAPEN Foundation is dedicated to OA, peer-reviewed books, operating two platforms: the [OAPEN Library](#), a central repository for hosting and disseminating OA books; and, in partnership with OpenEdition, the Directory of Open Access Books ([DOAB](#)), an aggregator and discovery service for OA books. Publishers can apply to join OAPEN & DOAB if they publish academic, peer reviewed books that are made freely available, or published under an open licence (such as a Creative Commons licence).

As part of Thoth's dissemination services, publishers can benefit from Thoth Open Metadata's collaboration agreement with OAPEN and DOAB. With this agreement, Thoth Open Metadata acts on behalf of the publishers subsumed under the umbrella of the Thoth OAPEN Publishing Collective and provides a streamlined way of submitting books to the OAPEN and DOAB catalogues on behalf of those participating publishers, and individual per-book fees will be waived.

OAPEN and DOAB provide multiple options to facilitate ingest of data from publishers. Inclusion in DOAB requires an initial declaration of a publisher's peer review processes, which will be assessed by OAPEN staff. Once accepted, content submitted to OAPEN will also automatically be ingested into DOAB. To operationalise documentation of

publishers' peer review practices, DOAB has introduced the [Peer Review Information Service for Monographs \(PRISM\)](#), a descriptive set of additional metadata fields stored within DOAB and provided through the [OPERAS service catalogue](#).

As part of Thoth Open Metadata's close collaboration with OAPEN and DOAB via the [Trusted Platform Network](#), the team is currently scoping the integration of peer review information within the Thoth metadata schema. Ideally, this could then directly be submitted to DOAB as part of the general book registration process. This is part of a larger development package to facilitate a more automated, direct metadata exchange between OAPEN, DOAB, and Thoth, by streamlining data submission to OAPEN's DSpace repository via the [SWORD](#) protocol.

OAPEN key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	ONIX 3.0 (OAPEN specification). Other accepted formats: DOCX, XLSX, CSV, ONIX 2.1
Data delivery mode	email (standard); SFTP (select aggregators); SWORD protocol (select infrastructures), passive harvesting via OAI PMH (select aggregators); web interface upload (for individual publisher uploads)
Particularities	Thema subject classifications required as part of the general set of metadata delivery; No chapter-level data.
Handling of book cover files	extracted from main book file
Content files	PDF, EPUB
Chapter support	No (not on the level of individual chapters)
Provision of usage data	Through internal OAPEN dashboard (guidance) , with underlying data openly available via OPERAS Metrics
Automated Thoth workflow	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/OAPEN

Directory of Open Access Book (DOAB) key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	see OAPEN.
Data delivery mode	
Particularities	see OAPEN. Peer review documentation required. Usage of PRISM optional.
Handling of book cover files	extracted from main book file via OAPEN upload
Content files	Metadata only

Chapter support	No (not on the level of individual chapters)
Provision of usage data	Through internal OAPEN dashboard (guidance) , with underlying data openly available via OPERAS Metrics
Automated Thoth workflow	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/DOAB

JSTOR

JSTOR is a digital library for the scholarly community, managed by non-profit ITHAKA. JSTOR focuses mainly on articles, but has been increasing its range with monographs and edited collections. JSTOR has a dedicated [Open Access collection](#).

As part of Thoth's dissemination services, publishers can benefit from Thoth Open Metadata's umbrella agreement with JSTOR. With this agreement, Thoth acts on behalf of the publishers subsumed under the umbrella and provides a streamlined way of submitting books to the JSTOR archive on behalf of those participating publishers, and the standard per-book hosting fee is waived. Thoth Open Metadata facilitates review of the press by the JSTOR editors. The review will make sure the press is a good fit for the books programme per their [editorial guidelines](#).

Books submitted to JSTOR are automatically separated into individual chapters, and provided with stable URLs and DOIs, sometimes in conflict with already extant persistent identifiers (for more on this, see [van Gerven Oei et al. 2025](#)). To ensure publishers retain full control over the DOIs they register through the Thoth platform, Thoth Open Metadata has intentionally opted out of any additional DOI registration or multiple-resolution arrangements offered by JSTOR. This approach is intended to prevent the same publication from being assigned duplicate DOIs and to avoid conflicting metadata records.

As of Q3/2025, JSTOR has paused intake of new Open Access-only publishers, with a restart date yet to be confirmed.

JSTOR's key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	ONIX 3.0 (JSTOR specification). Other accepted formats: XLSX, ONIX 2.1
Data delivery mode	FTP
Particularities	At least one BISAC subject code required; more information available in the Metadata fields spreadsheet .
Handling of book cover files	JPEG, GIF, PNG, TIFF 6.0
Content files	PDF, EPUB

Chapter support	Yes. Book files delivered by the publisher are split into individual chapters by JSTOR
Provision of usage data	via JSTOR-internal dashboard (access can be requested on a per-publisher basis). More information available in JSTOR's guidance on Usage Reports .
Automated Thoth workflow	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/jstor

Project MUSE

Project MUSE is an online scholarly library managed by John Hopkins University and focused on the Humanities and Social Sciences. Project MUSE's [Open Access Books Program](#) offers publishers the ability to have their open access content available on the MUSE platform. OA books are fully integrated with all the features and functionality of subscriber-only books on Project MUSE.

As part of the Project MUSE [Open Access Book programme](#), the non-profit platform – established as a partnership between Johns Hopkins University Press and the Milton S. Eisenhower Library – encourages publishers to submit EPUB files alongside the standard provision of PDFs that are the basis of MUSE's general books programme. For open access titles, EPUBs submitted to Project MUSE will be converted to HTML5 to create a browser-native interface.

As part of Thoth's dissemination services, publishers can benefit from Thoth Open Metadata's umbrella agreement with Project MUSE. With this agreement, Thoth Open Metadata acts on behalf of the publishers subsumed under the umbrella and provides a streamlined way of submitting books to the MUSE platform on behalf of those participating publishers. Thoth Open Metadata reviews each new publisher wishing to distribute to MUSE as per their normal protocols. MUSE can only work with non-profit presses with regards to the OA books programme.

Project MUSE charges a per-title submission fee for each book listed on its platform, including for open access titles. As of 2024, Thoth Open Metadata and Project MUSE have agreed on a substantial reduction of that nominal per-title fee for titles being submitted through Thoth's dissemination workflows.

Books submitted to Project MUSE are automatically separated into individual chapters, and provided with stable URLs and DOIs, sometimes in conflict with already extant persistent identifiers (for more on this, see van Gerven Oei et al. 2025). To ensure publishers retain full control over the DOIs they register through the Thoth platform, Thoth Open Metadata have intentionally opted out of any additional DOI registration or multiple-resolution arrangements offered by Project MUSE. This approach is intended to prevent the same publication from being assigned duplicate DOIs and to avoid conflicting metadata records.

Project MUSE key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	ONIX 3.0 (Project MUSE specification). Other accepted formats: ONIX 2.1, proprietary XLSX template
Data delivery mode	FTP; uploader tool
Particularities	At least one BIC or BISAC subject code required; see Metadata fields spreadsheet . Further guidance on the preparation of PDFs and EPUBs, including naming conventions, is available via the Thoth Wiki . Project MUSE generally asks for metadata for new books one quarter in advance.
Handling of book cover files	Delivery of separate cover files required in JPEG, GIF, or PNG
Content files	PDF, EPUB (for open access titles)
Chapter support	Yes
Provision of usage data	via quarterly xls spreadsheet, and through Project MUSE's internal statistics portal .
Automated Thoth workflow	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/project-muse

EBSCO

EBSCO operates multiple platforms, each characterised by distinct submission requirements. For instance, [GOBI](#), which accepts only printed works, requires publishers to physically submit hardcopies. Metadata for titles submitted to GOBI is generated in-house by GOBI and subsequently disseminated to its library network. To provide an example, all printed orders from UK publishers, including those for GOBI, are first sent to a UK-based agent before being shipped to the United States, despite the availability of US-based printing facilities.

Many libraries, particularly in the UK, use GOBI as a procurement platform. An inclusion of open access book metadata in GOBI would therefore be useful to enable acquisitions librarians to identify when requested titles that they are trying to order are actually freely available as open access books. That metadata input is thus less aimed at improving discoverability for the general public end-users/readers, and more about discoverability for librarians, so that they can avoid paying for expensive ebook licences when an actual open access version is available (so-called 'double-dipping').

Next to GOBI, EBSCO is also working to introduce [MOSAIC](#) as a new library procurement platform.

Within EBSCO's portfolio, full-text PDFs and EPUBs of long-form scholarship can be deposited in [EBSCO eBooks](#), the company's dedicated ebook library service. Provision of

pre-publication metadata and content is encouraged as soon as possible, utilising either an EBSCO flavour of ONIX 2.1, or a proprietary XLSX file.

[EBSCOhost](#) similarly accepts ONIX files and ebook files (PDF, EPUB) to be uploaded via FTP. Since the introduction of the EBSCOhost open access ebook collection, open access content can be submitted at no cost. A bespoke naming convention is in place for ebook files submitted. An email alert needs to be sent upon upload of new content.

It seems noteworthy here to highlight that this collection is not publicly available but remains login-walled to EBSCOhost subscriber institutions. Users looking to access this collection are required to authenticate/log in to EBSCOhost via their institution (e.g., via Shibboleth or EZproxy authentication) prior to being able to access the DRM-free content included in the EBSCOhost open access ebook collection.

[EBSCO Knowledge Base](#), a service used by libraries to manage collections and help with content discoverability, allows the input of metadata in KBART that includes title, ISBN, URL, author(s), publisher, DOI, edition/volume number, and access type of the e-books, but not of metadata information related to the copyright/license of the title as a whole. This ultimately makes it difficult for publishers to flag content as open access.

Alongside EBSCO Knowledge Base, signing a full-text contract with EBSCO also appears to include indexation in [EBSCO Discovery](#) services, which again seems to be a different product. According to EBSCO's [official documentation](#), "both the discovery service and the Knowledge Base are part of the EBSCO Discovery Solution (EDS), but different types of data are required. EDS typically needs more granular data, and the Knowledge Base only requires title-level information."

As part of Thoth dissemination services, publishers can benefit from Thoth Open Metadata's umbrella agreement with EBSCO eBooks. Through this agreement, Thoth Open Metadata acts on behalf of the publishers subsumed under the umbrella and provides a streamlined way of submitting books to the eBooks platform and knowledgebases on behalf of those participating publishers.

EBSCO eBooks key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	ONIX 2.1 (EBSCO specification). Other accepted formats: proprietary XLSX template
Data delivery mode	FTP
Particularities	See Metadata fields spreadsheet
Handling of book cover files	Not specified as separate entities
Content files	PDF, EPUB
Chapter support	Yes
Provision of usage data	Per-publisher usage reports can be requested via EBSCO Product

	Relation Manager contact
Automated Thoth workflow	✔ Yes
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/EBSCO-ebooks

EBSCO Knowledge Base key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	KBART (OCLC specification). XLSX, CSV, MARC, XML & tab-delimited text also supported
Data delivery mode	FTP, email. Email alerts need to be sent upon upload of new content.
Particularities	See Metadata fields spreadsheet
Handling of book cover files	N/A
Content files	Metadata only
Chapter support	Yes
Provision of usage data	tbd.
Automated Thoth workflow	✔ Yes
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/EBSCO-Knowledge-Base

ProQuest / Ex Libris (Clarivate)

Under the Clarivate umbrella, ProQuest and Ex Libris operate as closely linked but distinct units, with ProQuest controlling significant scholarly content and data assets and Ex Libris supplying a dominant library management and discovery infrastructure.

ProQuest's [Ebook Central](#) is an ebook platform for research, discovery, selection, acquisition and administration for libraries which hosts book files in PDF and/or EPUB format.

Similar to EBSCOhost (see above), the open access titles listed in Ebook Central are not accessible to the public but remain login-walled to ProQuest subscriber institutions. Users looking to access this collection are required to authenticate/log in to ProQuest's portal via their institution (e.g., via Shibboleth or EZproxy authentication) prior to being able to access the DRM-free content included in Ebook Central.

Alongside this content-hosting platform, ProQuest offers a variety of Knowledge Bases via [Ex Libris'](#) service offers. Subscribing customers can use these Knowledge Bases (implemented through Alma, SFX and 360KB) to manage individual or consortial subscriptions and holdings, and to enable link resolvers to get the end-user from a search result in Ex Libris discovery products (Summon and Primo) to the item's full text

in the provider’s native platform. Once collections are loaded into the Knowledge Bases, each subscribing customer then has the option to either select and activate relevant packages, or pick relevant individual titles from the list.

As part of Thoth’s dissemination services, publishers can benefit from Thoth Open Metadata’s umbrella agreement with ProQuest Ebook Central. With this agreement, Thoth acts on behalf of the publishers subsumed under the umbrella and provides a streamlined way of submitting books to the Ebook Central platform, Knowledgebases and CDI, and Alma Community Zone on behalf of those participating publishers.

As of February 2025, Clarivate, the parent company of ProQuest Ex Libris, have essentially removed ProQuest offers from the library book acquisition marketplace and are also working to sunset OASIS, their procurement platform. Clarivate [no longer offer individual print book purchasing](#) and is phasing out one-time perpetual purchases of digital collections and e-books. Instead, Clarivate is moving to a subscription-only model for ebooks, with libraries being asked to pay annually for a changing/changeable corpus of ca. 700k ebooks, with no perpetual access rights. This has led to wide-spread negative reactions from subscribing libraries, with many deciding to cease purchasing from ProQuest Ebook Central (see, e.g., Haimé 2025).

ProQuest eBook Central key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	ONIX 2.1 (ProQuest specification). ONIX 3, or proprietary xls template also supported.
Data delivery mode	FTP
Particularities	See Metadata fields spreadsheet
Handling of book cover files	JPG
Content files	PDF, EPUB
Chapter support	Yes
Provision of usage data	tbd.
Automated Thoth workflow	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/ProQuest-Ebook-Central

Ex Libris Knowledge Bases (Alma, SFX and 360KB) key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	KBART (OCLC specification). UTF-8 encoded text (.txt), Excel (.xls/.xlsx), CSV, MARC records (for books only), and some types of XML data (depending on schema used and data elements available) also supported.
Data delivery mode	passive/harvesting, FTP (push), FTP (pull)

Particularities	See Metadata fields spreadsheet
Handling of book cover files	N/A
Content files	Metadata only
Chapter support	Yes, chapter metadata only
Provision of usage data	tbd.
Automated Thoth workflow	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/Ex-Libris

Ex Libris Central Discovery Index (CDI) key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	XML (including XML in Dublin Core/XML with NLM DTD/XML with ONIX DTD/XML with custom DTD/Custom XML without DTD), Delimited Text Format (Tab Delimited or CSV), ONIX and BITS for book/chapter-level metadata, JSON, MARC21/MARC UNIMARC (binary/.mrc files – not ASCII/.mrk files)/MARCXML, Excel spreadsheets (.xls/.xlsx)
Data delivery mode	FTP (push), FTP (pull), OAI MPH (harvesting), HTTP link to download files
Particularities	See Metadata fields spreadsheet
Handling of book cover files	N/A
Content files	Metadata only
Chapter support	Yes, chapter metadata only
Provision of usage data	tbd.
Automated Thoth workflow	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/Ex-Libris

OCLC WorldCat

OCLC WorldCat is the world's largest library catalog, a closed, cooperative database created and maintained by tens of thousands of member libraries across the globe. It contains a comprehensive list of library collections, including not just books but also digital media, historic documents, and unique items. It can be searched by the general public on WorldCat.org to find out what libraries hold specific items and where to find them.

It seems noteworthy that OCLC enforces a particularly strict control regime on the metadata held in its database, which means that data originating from OCLC's WorldCat cannot easily be shared or re-used in other contexts outside of the OCLC ecosystem.¹²

As part of Thoth's dissemination services, Thoth can act on behalf of publishers to provide an automated way of submitting book metadata records to [OCLC Knowledgebase](#) into the Thoth Open Metadata Collection. The 'upstream' high-quality metadata created and managed by publishers via Thoth will always remain open under a CC0 dedication.

Via [OCLC's WorldShare Management Services](#) (WMS), OCLC also is a major Library Management System provider. Hence, there are libraries tied into OCLC WorldCat metadata not just via an OCLC Cataloguing and Metadata subscription, but because their LMS relies on WorldCat as a centralised source for metadata (in a similar way to Clarivate's Ex Libris Alma, and the Alma Community Zone). It seems relevant to note the role of OCLC Collection Manager for ebook collections for OCLC Customers who do not have WMS as their Library Management System. With an OCLC Cataloguing and Metadata Subscription, a library can automate MARC record delivery for the ebook collections they 'select' in Collection Manager. Records are sent via SFTP, and an LMS like Alma can be configured to retrieve them and import them into 'local' collections. For Alma customers, this is an alternative to activating ebook collections in the Community Zone. It can mean access to better-quality records, with the above caveat that OCLC records are strictly controlled and not open for reuse by non-OCLC customers. All of this creates yet another locked-in "walled-garden" scenario where data created within the system cannot leave this specific environment. This practice appears antithetic to claims of interoperability and openness.

OCLC WorldCat key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	KBART (OCLC specification). Spreadsheet also supported
Data delivery mode	passive/harvesting FTP (push), FTP (pull)
Particularities	See Metadata fields spreadsheet
Handling of book cover files	N/A
Content files	Metadata only
Chapter support	Yes, metadata only
Provision of usage data	Individual download stats unavailable but a request for how many libraries are accessing a particular collection can be requested via email

¹² See also [Moody 2024](#). For more details on why many open data advocates are arguing for permissive open public domain-like licenses and dedications such as CC0 instead of the more restrictive OCLC-mandated ODC-By license, see e.g., van Gerven Oei, 2020.

Automated Thoth workflow	✔ Yes
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/Google-Play-Books

Web of Science - Book Citation Index (Clarivate)

The Web of Science is an integrated research platform that consolidates diverse content types, including journal articles, patents, websites, conference proceedings, and open-access materials, within a single interface. A key component of this platform, the Web of Science Core Collection, encompasses over a century of indexed research across the sciences, social sciences, and arts and humanities. This collection comprises ten indexes aggregating data from a vast array of scholarly journals, books, book series, and conferences. Notably, the [Book Citation Index \(BKCI\)](#) serves as a multidisciplinary resource covering literature in the sciences, social sciences, and humanities.

New publishers seeking to be considered for a partnership are evaluated by the BKCI Editorial Team. For publishers utilising Thoth's dissemination services, this connection will be facilitated on behalf of the publisher. To be considered for BKCI, publishers are asked to provide a link to their website, a short description of the publishing house, and an outline of their peer review and editorial policies. Publishers must have 10-20 titles in their catalogue ready for evaluation. If it is clear that the majority of a publisher's catalogue and policies do not align with BKCI priorities and/or any of the criteria detailed [here](#), a partnership will not be established. Publishers may re-apply in the future if subsequent books meet requirements.

Web of Science Book Citation Index (BKCI) key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	CSV
Data delivery mode	FTP
Particularities	See Metadata fields spreadsheet
Handling of book cover files	n/a
Content files	PDF
Chapter support	Yes
Provision of usage data	Not available
Automated Thoth workflow	✔ Yes
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/Web-of-Science

Jisc National Bibliographic Knowledgebase (NBK)

Jisc's [National Bibliographic Knowledgebase](#) (NBK) is a library index that allows for searching for library materials across the UK. Known as a union catalogue, it allows for searching for a book or journal across all subscribing member libraries at once.

The NBK is the most complete aggregation of UK academic, national and specialist library metadata available. Jisc's Library Hub cataloguing service provides access to comprehensive bibliographic data, collated by NBK and made available free of charge to Jisc members and to libraries that contribute data to the NBK.

It seems pertinent to highlight the distinction between the NBK as the 'data-lake', and Library Hub as the 'services' built on top of NBK. Jisc NBK members contribute metadata (MARC records) to the NBK, all of which can be searched for the purposes of discovery and comparison/benchmarking via Library Hub Discover and Library Hub Compare.

However, Library Hub Cataloguing does not offer members full access to the NBK data-lake. Due to existing restrictive licensing of parts of the database that originate from commercial vendors, Jisc cannot enable 'Cataloguing' access to any MARC records that are not free for sharing and reuse, i.e. vendor-supplied or shelf-ready records (from framework suppliers or BDS) and OCLC records.

Any CC0 MARC records shared with the NBK will not be restricted from inclusion in Library Hub Cataloguing – but while Library Hub Cataloguing itself is publicly available, libraries have to be a Jisc member to use it.

Jisc NBK key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	MARC
Data delivery mode	Amazon S3 bucket
Particularities	n/a
Handling of book cover files	tbd.
Content files	tbd.
Chapter support	tbd.
Provision of usage data	tbd.
Automated Thoth workflow	🚫 No - work-in-progress
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/Jisc-NBK

Amazon

Amazon's ecosystem plays an important role in publishers' dissemination strategies for both 'traditional' sales and open access titles. It seems baffling that dissemination of publishers' content to Amazon's systems remains highly opaque for any small-to-medium sized publisher seeking to participate in the Amazon marketplace. The Thoth Open Metadata team has spent more than a year in conversations with the provider to obtain more information on ways to facilitate data transfers into the Amazon network of products.

Amazon key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	ONIX 3 and XLSX
Data delivery mode	FTP, Amazon Publish to Kindle system via manual upload
Particularities	See Metadata fields spreadsheet
Handling of book cover files	Yes, format not specified.
Content files	EPUB
Chapter support	No
Provision of usage data	xlsx or txt document. Amazon provides download reports per region. Download of those reports is required within 15 days following the end of the reporting month.
Automated Thoth workflow	No - work-in-progress
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/Amazon

Google Play Books

[Google Play Books](#), formerly Google Ebooks, is the ebook distribution platform of Google, available in 75+ countries. Users can purchase and download ebooks from [Google Play](#), which offers over five million titles. Books can be read through a web browser, through the use of a mobile app available for Android and iOS, and through the use of select e-readers that offer support for Adobe Digital Editions.

The backend is rudimentary, and it appears this particular platform is underresourced in comparison to the rest of Google's service portfolio.

As part of Thoth's dissemination services, publishers can benefit from a streamlined way of submitting books to the [Google Books Partner Program](#). Publishers must create an individual Books Partner Centre account and then add Thoth as a user to their account to grant access for book catalog management.

Google Play Books key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	ONIX 3.0 (Google specification). Spreadsheet and ONIX 2.1 also supported.
Data delivery mode	Upload via Book Catalog in the Google Partner Center; Automated content fetch via Google Cloud bucket
Particularities	ISBN a requirement. More, see Metadata fields spreadsheet
Handling of book cover files	Yes, JPG
Content files	EPUB, PDF
Chapter support	Yes
Provision of usage data	Available via OPERAS Metrics
Automated Thoth workflow	Yes
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/Google-Play-Books

Royal National Institute of Blind People (RNIB) Bookshare

The UK-based RNIB works with publishers to provide their accessible files through [RNIB Bookshare](#) for use by learners with a print disability at all educational levels, from early years through to higher education.

As part of Thoth's dissemination services, Thoth will act on behalf of publishers to provide a streamlined way of submitting books to RNIB Bookshare. RNIB Bookshare will use EPUB or RTF files to automatically make the title available in a range of accessible formats. Where PDF only is supplied, the book will only be available to download by members as a PDF. More [guidance](#) on uploading content.

RNIB key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	ONIX 2.1, ONIX 3.0
Data delivery mode	FTP, web upload form
Particularities	ISBN a requirement
Handling of book cover files	n/a
Content files	EPUB2, EPUB3, RTF, PDF
Chapter support	Yes
Provision of usage data	Usage reports for download figures can be requested on a per-publisher basis (a recurring email report can be set up)
Automated Thoth workflow	No - work-in-progress

Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/RNIB-Bookshare
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Ulibros

Hosted by the Association of University Publishers in Latin America and the Caribbean / Asociación de Editoriales Universitarias de América Latina y el Caribe (EULAC), [Ulibros](#) seeks to optimise, standardise, and facilitate the management of metadata by EULAC publishers.

Hosting a variety of different collections (thematic, per publisher), Ulibros has a repository with more than 74,000 enriched metadata references, covering the publications of more than 350 university publishers from Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Ecuador, El Salvador, Mexico, Guatemala, Panama, Peru, Uruguay, and Venezuela. Open Access titles are listed in one of Ulibro's [subsections](#).

Ulibros is currently partnering with external provider [SIMEH](#) for its metadata management facilitation. Both the Ulibros platform and SIMEH are run by Hipertexto - Netizen, a commercial company with offices in Colombia and Mexico that is also [partnering with Metabooks](#), part of German books infrastructure oligopolist [MVB](#).

Ulibros key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	ONIX 3.0 (Thoth specification)
Data delivery mode	email
Particularities	tbd.
Handling of book cover files	tbd.
Content files	Metadata only
Chapter support	tbd.
Provision of usage data	n/a - the platform links to publishers' book pages, so usage stats will be counted via each publisher's webpage/catalogue.
Automated Thoth workflow	No - work-in-progress
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/Ulibros

Bookinfo

[Bookinfo](#) is a Brazil-based commercial book aggregator active in Latin America.

Bookinfo key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	ONIX 3.0 (Thoth specification).
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	Spreadsheet and API also supported.
Data delivery mode	FTP, or email.
Particularities	tbd.
Handling of book cover files	tbd.
Content files	EPUB, PDF
Chapter support	tbd.
Provision of usage data	tbd.
Automated Thoth workflow	🚫 No - tbd.
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/Bookinfo

Rakuten Kobo

Rakuten Kobo, a Japanese online bookstore, offers eBooks, audiobooks, newspapers, and magazines, mainly in the ePub format with DRM. Kobo does not have open access titles with an open license available via their storefront, but offers a variety of [free](#) titles.

Kobo key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	ONIX 3.0 (Kobo specification)
Data delivery mode	FTP
Particularities	tbd.
Handling of book cover files	tbd.
Content files	EPUB
Chapter support	No
Provision of usage data	Download reports sent monthly via email. Commercial (closed access book) reports are delivered automatically; for open access books, they must be requested
Automated Thoth workflow	🚫 No
Thoth Wiki entries	n/a

SciELO Livros

The [SciELO Livros](#) (SciELO Books) portal hosts national and thematic collections of academic publications with the aim of enhancing the visibility, accessibility, usage, and

scholarly impact of the research findings, essays, and studies it disseminates. All titles undergo a thorough peer review process and are selected by a scientific committee.

There are two main types of SciELO Collections: publisher collections, containing titles selected and recommended by participating publishers’ editorial committees, and thematic collections, featuring titles chosen by publishers or specialist groups and endorsed by a publisher’s editorial committee.

SciELO Books operates as part of the SciELO Program and is developed and funded by a consortium consisting of the publishers of Universidade Estadual Paulista Júlio de Mesquita Filho (UNESP), Universidade Federal da Bahia (UFBA), and Fundação Oswaldo Cruz (FIOCRUZ). Its methodology and technological platform were developed with the technical collaboration of BIREME/PAHO/WHO, and its implementation is supported by the Fundação de Apoio à Universidade Federal de São Paulo. SciELO Books is a member of the DOAB Trusted Partner Network.

SciELO Books offers its eBooks in PDF and ePUB formats through its official website, and via major commercial distributors, including Kobo Books, Google Bookstore, Amazon, and EBSCO.

SciELO Books key metadata requirements:

Preferred metadata format	ONIX 3.1
Data delivery mode	multiple
Particularities	tbd.
Handling of book cover files	tbd.
Content files	EPUB, PDF
Chapter support	yes
Provision of usage data	in xlsx format, sent to publishers on a monthly basis.
Automated Thoth workflow	🚫 No - work-in-progress
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/SciELO-Books

Open Book Collective

The Open Book Collective (OBC) is a non-profit charity registered in the UK, bringing together publishers, publishing service providers, and scholarly libraries to secure the diversity and financial futures of open access book production and dissemination.

In 2025, OBC introduced a dedicated metadata policy to make participating publishers aware of the benefits of open metadata. The policy urges publishers to make their

metadata available through the Thoth platform, to ensure inclusion of their scholarly outputs within the collective's joint catalogue.

In doing so, OBC has defined a set of required and recommended metadata fields that are deemed crucial to the successful running of their outreach campaigns to libraries – as, e.g., contributor affiliation data is used to reach out to libraries of these contributors' home institutions.

Details about the OBC's required and recommended metadata elements have been documented in the [main metadata schema comparison spreadsheet](#).

Crossref

Crossref is a non-profit membership organisation established in 2000, and based in the United States, that serves as one of the primary Digital Object Identifier (DOI) Registration Agencies. It provides persistent identifiers and metadata infrastructure that enable citation linking, long-term discoverability, and reliable access across scholarly communication. While initially focused on journals, Crossref has become increasingly important for book publishing, where the assignment of DOIs at both title and chapter level enhances visibility, facilitates interoperability with discovery services, and supports usage and citation tracking. Services such as Crossmark further expand this ecosystem by documenting updates, corrections, and retractions over time.

Crossref has [extensive documentation](#) available on how to construct DOI registration data files for books and chapters. To make this easier for publishers who are not fully familiar with structuring XML, Thoth provides a Crossref-compliant XML export, freely available to publishers. This output enables publishers to manually register their DOIs with Crossref if they choose to manage the process independently.

For publishers seeking automated workflows, Thoth's dissemination service includes Crossref membership via Thoth's Sponsorship. This means any subscribing press can generate DOIs directly through the Thoth interface, making use of streamlined workflows that handle both initial registration and metadata deposits on their behalf.

Thoth's Crossref XML output has also implemented the additional metadata required to participate in the [Crossmark](#) service, enabling publishers to signal the current status of a record (including corrections, retractions, or updates). Publishers participating in Crossref Sponsorship via Thoth's dissemination services can thus benefit from both DOI generation and full Crossmark integration – which in turn will benefit their metadata quality assessment introduced by Crossref via their Member Participation reports¹³.

Beyond initial registrations, both the freely available Crossref XML export and the automated Thoth dissemination workflows can also be used for regular maintenance and updating of Crossref records through metadata update deposits, ensuring that records remain accurate and current throughout the lifecycle of a publication.

¹³ see e.g., Open Book Publishers' [Crossref Participation report](#) as a good-practice example.

DataCite

At the time of writing, Thoth Open Metadata has not looked into DataCite in more detail, hence the lack of information on long-form-specific metadata. In late Q3/2025, Thoth Open Metadata has started to engage with DataCite, to see if an automated book submission route similar to the Crossref DOI registration workflow and sponsorship arrangement could be established.

Early conversations with the DataCite team have been very positive, and the two institutions will be looking to resume conversations in 2026.

Caveat: The Leaky Metadata Pipeline – Metadata Quality Deterioration Across the Book Supply Chain

In an ideal world, metadata, enabled via open licensing and interoperable interfaces, can flow freely between different platforms and stakeholders, and subsequently benefit from iterative improvement as participants from a variety of backgrounds contribute information to a given record.

As noted, e.g., by van Gerven Oei (2020), the reality is far removed from such a utopian scenario, which has led to a systemic issue that might be dubbed the “leaky metadata pipeline” – denoting the iterative loss of information that takes place when metadata records are being translated from one format to the other (e.g., from MARC to KBART), and are flowing across a variety of closed systems that restrict subsequent access to the information within.

As van Gerven Oei (2020) notes

“There is no doubt that many of the stakeholders in the scholarly communications chain make significant investments into creating metadata records, and it is perhaps a feature of the current closed and compartmentalised book metadata ecosystem that much of these investments are actually unnecessary double work.”

During recent years, more and more librarians have outlined the multiple issues that such a compartmentalised approach to metadata management creates across scholarly communications (see e.g., Auclair et. al. 2024). The complexities particular to the discovery and ingest of metadata related to long-form outputs seem to further amplify these issues, and open access title discovery then adds more issues on top of the existing ones (see e.g., Booth 2023; Edmunds 2023).

Numerous examples to illustrate these systemic issues can be drawn from the library world: Libraries that are tied into subscription framework agreements with major commercial aggregators have reported consistent sub-par quality metadata delivered by large-scale aggregators such as ProQuest Ebook Central, EBSCOhost, and OCLC that are arriving in their library’s management systems.

In the national context of the UK, MARC records for Ebook Central content are made available to library customers via an Admin portal and Acquisition Catalogue called LibCentral. Those MARC records come in two flavours, called Full MARC and Express MARC. Problems have been indicated with both versions, particularly in relation to missing MARC fields, inaccurate data in MARC fields, incorrect MARC field usage, incorrect field-data formatting (e.g., title data supplied in ALL CAPS, or otherwise mangled). One might expect the Full MARC records to contain more data than the Express MARC records, however, this is frequently not the case, e.g., 505 Contents fields and 520 Summary/abstract fields present in Express MARC files are missing from Full MARC files.

Looking at another scenario to illustrate the issue of leaky metadata pipelines, Ex Libris' ingestion processes use the KBART format, which means that much data is lost during ingestion because of the format's focus on collection-level information, as KBART is only designed to convey limited title list and coverage data. This in turn leads to poor metadata quality in the Alma Community Zone and Central Discovery Index (CDI) for many eBook collections and titles. Ex Libris does post-ingestion enrichment, but this is variable in terms of how long it takes and libraries often have to actively lobby via the Content section of the [Ex Libris Idea Exchange](#) for it to be actioned. All of that makes the metadata in Ex Libris knowledge bases extremely variable in terms of quality and completeness. And even when a publisher or provider has good-quality MARC records that they can share with the Ex Libris Provider Relations team, it is not straightforward to get this metadata ingested into the Community Zone or CDI.

Another prevailing bug reported by participating libraries leads to URLs in MARC records as delivered often pointing to the wrong page in Ebook Central, thus implying that a subscribing library does not have access to the title in question, when in fact the library does.

These examples point to a structural limitation of system-provider knowledge bases for disseminating ebook metadata to libraries that is particularly relevant for small-to-medium-sized publishers and university presses, because Ex Libris tends to prioritise bigger content providers for enrichment work.

What has furthermore been reported by librarians as deeply frustrating is the issue of open (CC0) metadata that is being shared with aggregators and knowledge base providers subsequently getting 'locked down' by virtue of the fact it has passed through a proprietary system. This in turn is understood to negatively impact stakeholders further along the supply chain, i.e., libraries and users/readers

Multiple librarians interviewed for this report have also noted that the ownership and control over many of these aggregator and discovery platforms exerted by for-profit entities such as Clarivate and EBSCO could be understood as being at the heart of these issues, as they are understood to have a vested interest in keeping 'their' data un-interoperable, and only share low-quality data with open scholarly infrastructures (see, e.g., van Eck and Waltman, 2025).

Many of those issues have long been prevalent across the whole scholarly communications ecosystem, and advocates have lately begun to address them via international initiatives such as the [Metadata2020](#) project, and the more recent [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) and Collaborative Metadata Enrichment Taskforce ([COMET](#)). Proposed actions have so far been largely focusing on journals.

Hence, the inception of the Thoth platform can be seen as an important intervention to address the issues particular to long-form publications, as it provides a fully open and free-to-use platform and flexible data model, which can in its entirety serve as an upstream source of open metadata.

VI. ARCHIVING: GENERALIST REPOSITORIES

Metadata is also useful to facilitate archiving of a publisher’s valuable contributions to the scholarly record for future generations. Small and scholar-led presses, constituting much of the "long tail" of publishers, often lack an active preservation policy. Recent studies highlight concerns over the archiving and preservation status of Open Access books, revealing risks associated with volatile cloud storage and the absence of preservation measures altogether (Laakso, 2023).

While larger publishers typically have agreements with “dark” digital preservation archives like CLOCKSS and Portico, small presses face challenges due to limited financial resources, institutional support, technical expertise, and staff resources (cf. Barnes et. al., 2022). Similar concerns extend to the long tail of open access journal publishers, prompting initiatives such as [Project JASPER](#) to address preservation gaps for OA journals lacking current preservation measures.

As part of the COPIM and Copim Open Book Futures projects, Thoth Open Metadata has been involved in the projects’ [Archiving & Digital Preservation](#) Work Package to scope the feasibility of implementing an open archiving approach (Higman et. al., 2024) via the Thoth Open Archiving Network (TOAN), with an initial focus on establishing automated submission workflows to generalist, “catch-all” repositories such as the Internet Archive or Zenodo.

Internet Archive

The [Internet Archive](#) is a digital library offering free universal access to knowledge. Anyone with a free account can upload materials via a drag/drop interface or an API.

Through Thoth Open Metadata’s dissemination services, publishers can seamlessly archive their publications with the Internet Archive, ensuring their content remains accessible for generations to come. To find out which books have already been stored in the Internet Archive through Thoth, see the [Thoth Open Archiving Network collection](#).

Internet Archive supports all kinds of digital materials, so it can accept a wide range of file formats, although individual chapters are not supported. Thoth maps published books to the Internet Archive concept of an item and supplies item-level and file-level metadata. Internet Archive metadata is retrieved in JSON format; as an example, the metadata for [this Thoth Open Archiving Network Item](#) can be viewed [in the browser](#). Internet Archive aims to be “metadata agnostic”, i.e. their data model is not constrained to fit any specific metadata standard. This allows Thoth to retain all of the rich metadata available in the database when content is uploaded.

Preferred metadata format	Custom format
Data delivery mode	Browser upload, API

Particularities	None
Handling of book cover files	n/a
Content files	PDFs submitted via the Thoth Open Archiving Network. Internet Archive accepts a wide variety of file types.
Chapter support	No
Provision of usage data	Total no. of page views listed for each item on its main page (also showing number of "favourites"), and for the collection as a whole in IA's About tab . IA also has a dedicated Views API available for more complex/powerful/granular usage data queries
Automated Thoth workflow	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/Internet-Archive

Zenodo

Zenodo is a general-purpose open-access repository initially developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artefacts. The repository is based on the open source [Invenio](#) research data management repository software. Data is stored in CERN's Data Centre. Both data files and metadata are kept in multiple online and independent replicas. To be an effective catch-all that eliminates barriers to adopting data sharing practices, Zenodo does not impose any requirements on format, size, access restrictions or licence. Next to the purpose of archiving long-form scholarship, publishers also use Zenodo as their primary outlet to store book content online, utilising the repository's in-built option to mint DOIs.

Preferred metadata format	Custom format
Data delivery mode	Browser upload, API
Particularities	None
Handling of book cover files	n/a
Content files	PDF, epub. Note that a wide set of file types are supported for upload, so sometimes also EPUB/XML can be submitted.
Chapter support	No
Provision of usage data	Total no. of page views listed for each item. Fully anonymised usage statistics also available via Zenodo API. In addition, Zenodo shares aggregated usage statistics with OpenAIRE Usage Counts as well as the DataCite service.

Automated Thoth workflow	No - work-in-progress
Thoth Wiki entries	https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/Zenodo

VII. ACCESSIBILITY METADATA

Accessibility metadata is rapidly becoming a critical component of the scholarly publishing ecosystem. While only a limited number of aggregator platforms currently require accessibility-related metadata, this situation is changing quickly. Recent and forthcoming legislation – such as the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA) Title II in the United States and the European Accessibility Act (EAA) in the European Union – will soon make the provision of accessibility metadata mandatory for most publishers distributing digital books in international markets.

Within this evolving landscape, Thoth Open Metadata is taking a leading role in ensuring that publishers can meet these new expectations through open, interoperable, and future-proof metadata practices. Recognising accessibility not only as a legal or technical requirement but as a cornerstone of equitable and inclusive scholarly communication, the Thoth team has been proactively extending its data model to accommodate accessibility-specific metadata. This work will enable publishers to capture, manage, and disseminate accessibility information seamlessly across all supported metadata outputs.

In doing so, Thoth aligns with recent recommendations from the W3C Accessibility Metadata Task Force, whose 2025 report offers comprehensive guidance for implementers “who wish to render accessibility metadata directly to users in understanding how to represent the accessibility claims inherent in machine-readable accessibility metadata in a user-friendly User Interface / User Experience” (LaPierre et al. 2025). The W3C guidance is primarily aimed at implementers such as bookstores, retailers, and distributors, but it is equally valuable for content creators and metadata managers seeking to ensure their data accurately reflects accessibility features. Implementation supplements are currently available for [ONIX](#) as well as [EPUB](#).

The upcoming Thoth data model extension, to be released in Q1/2026, will operationalise these principles across all supported export formats – including ONIX 3, MARC 21, KBART, and BIBFRAME – thereby equipping publishers with a coherent framework for compliance and discovery. This initiative reinforces Thoth’s commitment to reducing technical and administrative barriers for small and scholar-led publishers, while actively contributing to a more inclusive and accessible open access ecosystem.

Further details on accessibility metadata across formats:

- [MARC 21 – Accessibility](#)
- [ONIX 3 – Accessibility](#)
- [KBART – Accessibility](#)

- [BIBFRAME 2.0 – Accessibility](#)

For further information on accessibility implementation and inclusive publishing practices, readers are encouraged to consult the [Copim Compass guide on Accessibility](#).

VIII. EU GENERAL PRODUCT SAFETY REGULATION (GPSR)

Relevant to open access and non-open access titles alike, the [EU General Product Safety Regulation](#) (EU GPSR) introduced in 2025 is applicable to both print and online versions of titles sold within Europe. Publishers are required to carry out a risk assessment, retain technical information relating to safety testing, and ensure compliance with EU safety standards.

The GPSR mandates that retail websites and online marketplaces present product safety information in a clear, accessible, and structured format. Such information must not be provided solely as images (e.g., scanned warning labels) but in a machine-readable form compatible with screen readers and other assistive technologies. Warnings and instructions must be written in clear, comprehensible language appropriate to the marketplace’s primary language. Where technical terminology is used, a plain-language version must also be provided.

The following information is required:

- Accessibility data
- Name of publisher
- Name of imprint
- Product safety contact details, including physical address located within the EU
- For non-EU publishers: details of a nominated EU-based representative (this can be a sales agent, in-EU distributor, or other third party residing within the EU).

EDItEUR’s [Product Safety application note](#) provides a more detailed account of how publishers can implement required metadata within their reporting workflows through ONIX.

Thoth Open Metadata is currently working to implement all required metadata elements to ensure compliance with these regulations, giving publishers the ability to record the necessary information and output them via ONIX and other formats where relevant.

IX. EU DEFORESTATION REGULATION (EUDR)

The [EU Deforestation Regulation](#) (EUDR) had been understood to introduce new reporting requirements for all publishers seeking to sell print versions of their titles – be they Open Access or closed, commercial titles.

In October 2025, EDItEUR had released a detailed [application note](#) on how publishers can ensure they remain compliant with EUDR regulations.

In essence, the EUDR legislation distinguishes between “operators” and “traders” and provides a compliance timeline for micro- and small enterprises.¹⁴ As outlined in the application note, ONIX is deemed a suitable vehicle for communicating deforestation-related metadata such as Due Diligence Statements (DDS) and geolocation of raw materials, but EDItEUR also highlights that the standard may only be used to cover parts of the full supply chain (such as paper mills and printers) and may need to be complemented with other documentation.

It is understood that for each print run, provenance metadata would have needed to accumulate: a second (or third) run should include earlier and new data on paper stock used so that records reflect changes over time. While purely digital products are exempt and non-wood materials may pose fewer issues, physical printed books made of wood-based papers (such as those made available via Print-On-Demand/POD) have been deemed to squarely fall within scope if exported to the EU.

In a rather surprising last-minute amendment to a revision of the original EUDR legislation, the European Commission has, in its session of December 17, 2025, adopted the motion to adjust the scope of products covered by the EUDR (European Commission, 2025). As of this most recent amendment, printed products (which are understood to include printed books) are now being exempt from the scope of EUDR policy (UK Publishers Association, 2025).

This in turn means no further requirements will be put to publishers regarding provision of additional due diligence, or geolocation data at the level of individual titles. As the Federation of European Publishers (FEP) notes,

Even if books are excluded, paper is not, and the European Commission is carrying out a survey to gather information about the expected use of the Information System (TRACES) by companies importing EUDR commodities or derived products. (2025)

¹⁴ As Stewart (2024) notes, the smallest firms must comply by mid-2026, though they may need to supply data by the end of 2025. A recent EU negotiation draft, dated November 10, 2025, suggests deferring the law's application to December 30, 2026, for larger firms, and June 30, 2027, for smaller ones. At the time of writing, this suggestion has yet to be approved by the EU.

It remains to be seen if and what kinds of future obligations publishers might need to abide by.

X. METADATA RECOMMENDATIONS FOR BOOKS: PROPOSAL FOR A TWO-TIERED APPROACH

As noted by Stone et al. (2021), the 2019 Science Europe briefing underscored the need for high-quality technical standards for academic books, detailing conventional, digital, and OA-specific metadata elements, while the European Commission calls for standardised metadata to enhance usability. Stakeholders and various studies (Gregg et al. 2019; Adema & Stone 2017b; Deville et al. 2019; Adema 2019) advocate for establishing good/best practices and a minimum metadata requirement. An early attempt had been made by initiatives such as the Jisc/OAPEN metadata model for open access books, which was

[d]eveloped in consultation with research funders, academics and institutional staff and OA monograph publishers [and] recommends a provisional list of metadata for OA book publishers and other stakeholders. (Jisc/OAPEN 2016)¹⁵

As outlined in more detail in this report's Section III, Stone et al. (2021)'s review of the older Jisc/OAPEN model and accompanying scoping exercise yielded additional recommendations pertaining to book publishing that have proven incredibly useful.

Following a review of the variety of more recent reports and recommendations listed in Section III, and also considering the work undertaken within Thoth Open Metadata over the last six years in close exchange with a wide variety of publishers and partnering infrastructures active in the books publishing space across the globe, including the Public Knowledge Project (PKP), OAPEN, DOAB, the Open Book Collective, SciELO Livros, and the OPERAS network, a two-tiered set of metadata emerges.

The proposed two-tiered metadata model is defined as follows:

- **Essential Metadata:** to include essential information and DOIs at both the title and chapter levels. More specifically, these comprise: work type, work status, title, subtitle, contributor names, contribution type, copyright holder, DOI, license, publication date, place of publication, publication format, publisher / imprint (if applicable), language(s), landing page URL, full-text URL for the

¹⁵ The full 2026 Jisc / OAPEN metadata model for open access books, together with other stakeholder-specific metadata requirements, is documented in this report's [supplementary spreadsheet](#) for easy reference.

primary/canonical¹⁶ source of a title, page range (for chapters), ISBN, ISSN (for titles forming part of a series), and author/publisher-generated subject codes/headings (e.g., via free-text keywords, or controlled vocabularies such as Thema). Release of the metadata into the public domain made explicit in the metadata record (e.g., via a CC0 dedication in human- and machine-readable form).

- **Desirable Metadata:** to include cover image URLs, table of contents, abstract, references (at the level of the book and individual chapters), PIDs for contributor and funder information (i.e., ORCID for all contributors, with ISNI as optional extension, and ROR IDs¹⁷ for contributor affiliations and funders), contributor roles, location URLs of secondary sources where open access content can be accessed. Facilitation of multilingual metadata in languages other than English.
- **Additional Elements to consider:** a pricing element to explicitly denote “free of charge”, and supporting non-standard Latin script forms as metadata input. Peer-review status of a given work¹⁸.

It is worth noting here that some of the listed metadata fields remain idiosyncratic, as individual platforms and organisations use differing denominations for those fields, and their instances. One exemplary case in point is the wide range of existing definitions of `work type` to categorise long-form scholarly output: recent research conducted by Wake Hyde in close collaboration with Thoth Open Metadata has highlighted the existence of a wide variety of bespoke terms to denote similar concepts, with a lack of widely-adopted controlled vocabularies used to categorise long-form scholarly outputs (Wake Hyde, 2025).¹⁹

Below is a full list of metadata elements included in the proposed metadata model for both books and chapters, with an easily-accessible version also documented in this

¹⁶ A particularity of open access titles (full book, and individual chapters) is that its content can be hosted on more than one platform. For the purpose of defining the canonical / authoritative source of a publication, the authors advocate for this to be represented by the initial publisher-controlled web resource (e.g., publishers’ web page) where the original publication file has been hosted. It can be useful to also record URLs/locations of files hosted on third-party platforms that may host a publisher’s content to ensure wide dissemination (see also ‘Desirable Metadata’).

¹⁷ to [supersede Funder Registry / FundRef](#).

¹⁸ Recording peer-review information for long-form publishing is still an emerging practice, with no unified way of recording relevant information. Different platforms implement different categorisations. The [PRISM framework](#) developed via OPERAS and implemented as an optional descriptive standard within the [Directory of Open Access Books](#) is one notable option. More scoping and advocacy work will be needed to establish a common ground between the multiple stakeholders active in the book supply chain.

¹⁹ Next to Wake Hyde’s research, the German DINI consortium also maintains a comprehensive list of work types, including multiple (partially-)overlapping definitions for long-form publications. <https://intern.dini.de/confluence/display/GemVokabular/DINI+Vokabular>

report's [supplementary spreadsheet](#) (a version of this spreadsheet is also stored in the report's [Zenodo deposit](#) to facilitate easy re-use).

Field name	Description	Field type	Status
Essential			
work type	Work Type (e.g., Edited Collection, Monograph)	Controlled Vocabulary, with the option to add free text	Required
work status	Work Status (e.g., published, forthcoming, retracted, ...)	Controlled Vocabulary	Required
title	Title	Free text - separate fields for title and subtitle	Required
subtitle	Subtitle	Free text - separate fields for title and subtitle	Required
contributor names	Author/Editor/other contributor name(s) & ORCIDs (where available)	Free text, divided into Given Name(s) and Family Name(s)	Required
contribution type	role description	Controlled Vocabulary, implementing CReDIT, with the option to include additional roles not covered by the CReDIT taxonomy to accommodate needs from the Social Sciences and Humanities	Required
Copyright holder	Denomination of the copyright holder		Required
work license	Open License (e.g., Creative Commons), All rights reserved	Controlled List, incl. machine-readable URL of the license	Required
publication date	Publication Date in ISO format	Following ISO standard	Required
place of publication	Place of Publication	Free text	Required
publication format	clear denomination of publication format (PDF, ePub, HTML, etc.)	Controlled Vocabulary, with the option to add free text	Required
publisher / imprint (if applicable)	Publisher name, URL, ROR (encouraged)	Free text plus ROR PID	Required
DOI	DOI URL	Well-formatted DOI following best practice	Required
landing Page URL	DOI and/or Landing Page URL (where DOI is not used)	URL. Highly relevant in the context of collating usage statistics across multiple OA platforms	Required
full-text URL	URL of the full text document (link to the publication file, e.g., PDF, epub)	URL. Highly relevant in the context of collating usage statistics across multiple OA platforms	Required
page range (for chapters)		free text (to enable Roman numerals and other variations next to Arabic numbers)	Required
language	to indicate language(s) used in the publication	Controlled list following ISO standard	Required
ISBN	Book-level ISBNs (ideally one ISBN per book format)	standardised input, ideally via ISBN check upon entry	Required
ISSN	for serial publications	standardised	Required

subject codes / headings	via controlled vocabularies such as Thema or VIAF, free-text keyword option also enabled	Multiple controlled vocabularies, or free-text keyword as fallback	Required
metadata record license	Explicit mention of the license applied to a given metadata record, to enable downstream re-use	Standardised CC0 or other public domain dedication in both human- and machine-readable form	Required
Desirable			
cover image URLs	URL where the cover image can be accessed	URL	Recommended
table of contents	in free-text, Markdown, or JATS XML	Free text, preformatted (see desc.)	Recommended
abstract	in free-text, Markdown, or JATS XML	Free text, with possibility to record in multiple languages	Recommended
references / works cited	on the level of the book and/or individual chapters	CSV (can be a list of referenced DOIs at minimum)	Recommended
Contributor PIDs	ORCID where available; ISNI as alternative	ORCID number or full URL to profile	Recommended
Affiliated institution of Contributor	ROR	ROR ID or full URL to profile	Recommended
Funder information	ROR (to supersede Funder Registry)	ROR ID or full URL to profile	Recommended
Location URLs	Content URLs from the various platforms that OA content has been disseminated to	URL	Recommended
	ARK as alternative PID	ARK ID or full URL	Optional
	ISNI as alternative PID	ISNI ID or full URL	Optional
Multilingual versions of metadata	to enable publishers from different regional contexts to record metadata in languages other than English		Recommended
Peer-review status	To indicate the type of peer review applied to a given title.	Could be using PRISM framework, or other ways to denote peer-review status.	Optional
Crossmark	(for publishers using Crossref)	See Crossref guidance for more details	Optional

The full scope of this extended metadata framework has been implemented within Thoth's data model and is available for free in its entirety via the open-source and free-to-use self-service [Thoth metadata platform](#).

Caveat on Open Access markers

Throughout the last decades, there have been numerous calls to integrate open access markers into metadata schemata to enhance discoverability, including recent calls to specifically identify Diamond Open Access outputs (see e.g., Gatti et al. 2024, Barnes et al. 2025).

Actual implementation of these markers, however, remain complex. A work's open access status is commonly discerned from the work's underlying license rather than a simple metadata flag, as the application of a permissive open license is the only way to formally mark content as open access in a legally binding way. The matter is further complicated by ambiguous definition(s) of "open". For example, Open Educational Resources (OER) standards usually mandate highly permissive open licenses (e.g., CC0, CC BY), whereas scholarly OA publishing commonly applies a broader spectrum of licenses, including Creative Commons Non-Commercial (NC) or No-Derivatives (ND) markers, to accommodate the complexities inherent in long-form publishing that are understood to be difficult to reduce to a limited set of licenses.

Consequently, metadata recommendations should prioritise the signalling and exchange of well-formed licensing information, ideally including a persistent URI to the specific license deed.^{20,21}

This approach then enables individual communities to apply their own context-specific definition of 'openness' by utilising and interpreting the detailed license data, rather than relying on a simplified, universal marker. Such a strategy also mitigates predatory practices where content is made available gratis temporarily, but remaining under a closed 'All rights reserved' copyright, hence lacking the explicit permissions required for third-party reuse.

Taking a more specific look at Diamond open access, the Diamond model is commonly defined as content that, upon publication, is immediately released under an open-access license without any contributor- or reader-facing fees (e.g. Farge 2012, Fuchs & Sandoval 2013). One might argue that this definition could be broken down into two distinct – and thus separable – descriptive metadata elements: on the one hand, the denomination of "open access", on the other, the status of "no author or reader-facing fees". As has been established above, the former can easily be covered via checking for a permissive open license to infer a work's open access status. The latter, though – asking for information about author/contributor-facing charges (such as Article / Book Processing Charges aka APCs/BPCs) – points to a rather more complex issue.

As far as the authors are aware, there is no well-defined metadata framework that currently would allow for the recording of data pertaining to production costs or other

²⁰ The provision of this information is understood to be critical throughout the supply chain, and with a particular relevance to libraries.

²¹ The authors are aware of emerging initiatives to advance information flows either by signalling (as is being done by licensing frameworks) or by moderating standard sets of community-defined machine actionable metadata. Notable here are initiatives such as the [Creative Commons Signals](#) project, or applications of the Open Digital Rights Language ([ODRL](#)) made possible through dataspaces standardised by the emerging ISO Dataspace Protocol. The [participant rulebook](#) for the piloted OA Book Usage Data Trust (Drummond et. al. 2024) provides an example of how metadata disclosures can be required as a part of data intermediation workflows across organizations through a dataspace.

At the time of writing, wider implementation across the books ecosystem has so far not (yet) materialised, which makes future implications for publishers and platforms difficult to define.

charges levied by a publisher. One notable initiative, the German [openCost project](#) (Schweighofer & Bartlewski 2024), has developed a standardised model for journals that enables publishers to share cost-related information with libraries and other stakeholders such as the [openAPC database](#). The standardised openCost model has yet to be adapted to long-form publications. From a conceptual perspective, it might be argued that such an endeavour will remain difficult to implement because of the existing fragmentation within the international book publishing ecosystem, and a corresponding lack of standardised terminology to describe what costs and charges a publisher might opt to record in their production workflow. Hence, while calls for Diamond OA markers are understandable, an actual meaningful implementation of such a marker might prove difficult. It is thus suggested to keep a watching brief on emerging trends in this area.

XI. OUTLOOK

The proposed metadata framework is well-aligned with quality criteria as defined via existing standards published by regional and national initiatives, such as those released by the working group of German-speaking university publishers (Arbeitsgemeinschaft der Universitätsverlage 2023), and recommendations such as those to support wide-spread adoption of the UKRI Open Access policy (Brown et al. 2022; 2025), and the PALOMERA recommendations for OA books (Bandura-Morgan et al. 2024). Likewise, it is compatible with the current, journal-focused version of the Diamond OA Standard (2025) and is aligned with the open data principles advocated for e.g., via the international group of signatories of the [Barcelona Declaration](#) and the Collaborative Open Metadata Enhancement Task Force ([COMET](#)). Furthermore, the variety of requirements from different aggregators active across the book supply have also been taken into consideration, to ensure publishers are enabled to proactively collate all information necessary to facilitate wide dissemination of their valuable contributions to the scholarly record. Hence, the metadata framework is understood to be robust and flexible enough to accommodate both current needs and future developments in the OA publishing and policy landscape.

On a practical level, the framework at hand is already seeing actual and full implementation for both open access and closed access titles and chapters within the freely available Thoth metadata management platform, with exports of that high-quality open data available in the variety of formats and platform-specific flavours supported by the platform's APIs, and with all exports being released under a CC0 public domain dedication to facilitate easy downstream reuse. It has already proven useful to numerous publishers seeking to enhance their output's visibility, e.g., enabling them to excel in the metadata quality checks that Crossref is implementing via its Participation Reports.²²

²² See, e.g., the metadata quality assessment of Open Book Publishers, a UK-based not-for-profit Diamond OA publisher that has fully implemented the proposed metadata framework in their

Hence, the authors of this report encourage larger-scale adoption by a wider set of key stakeholders active in the book supply chain, including publishers, publishing platforms, aggregators, indices, and libraries.

A next step towards fostering a fuller adoption will include mapping the proposed model onto existing repository vocabularies such as the OpenAIRE and Coalition of Open Access Repositories (COAR) metadata frameworks that are being used by a large cross-section of institutional and generalist repositories across the globe. Further conversations to integrate the metadata framework with key stakeholders such as [Crossref](#) and [DataCite](#), with open publishing platforms such as PKP's Open Monographs Press (OMP), the [Janeway](#) publishing system, or [Pressbooks](#), with open [library management systems](#) such as Koha and Folio, and with the international community of research funders, e.g., via the OPERAS Policy Forum initiated via the PALOMERA project, will also be useful to raise broader awareness of the specific needs of long-form publishing.

Putting the optimised open metadata framework for books and chapters presented here into practice will enable publishers to collate rich, high-quality open metadata for both open and closed access titles, and will thus significantly improve the findability and re-use of publishers' long-form contributions to the scholarly record. A larger-scale adoption is thus encouraged to help with situating long-form publishing more centrally within a broader movement towards an adoption of open, community-owned interoperable infrastructure and standards across all forms of scholarly communication.

Ultimately, opening up the provision of metadata is deemed necessary to address persistent key challenges in scholarly publishing such as those presented by corporate tactics to tie scholars and small-to-medium-sized publishers into dependencies (so-called lock-in scenarios), by limiting the reuse of metadata through an application and enforcement of strict copyright to data that, due to its descriptive nature, is widely understood by experts to be largely non-copyrightable (see e.g. Courtney et. al., 2024), and by the continued corporate capture of publication and data outputs and outlets as practiced by big commercial entities (e.g. ICOLC, 2023).

day-to-day publishing practice, as reflected in Open Book Publishers' [Crossref Participation Report](#). The lack of Funder Registry IDs in those records is due to Thoth using ROR to identify funders, as it is understood that [Open Funder Registry IDs will eventually be deprecated, and replaced by ROR](#).

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